

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

**CONNECTING ON THEIR OWN TERMS:
COMMUNITY NETWORKS AND COLLECTIVE GOVERNANCE IN
COLOMBIA**

MASTER THESIS

to obtain the Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree in Digital Communication
Leadership (DCLead)

of

Faculty of Social Sciences

Paris Lodron University of Salzburg, Austria

Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences and Solvay Business School

Vrije Universiteit Brussels, Belgium

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Salzburg, 31 July 2025

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to the communities and individuals who generously shared their time, knowledge, and experiences for this research. You made me cry and smile as I learned about the strength and resilience of communities, proving that despite the violence of illegal groups, the exploitation by private conglomerates, and the neglect of the state, people continue to stand up for their rights. Please keep fighting for your sovereignty.

My sincere thanks go to my supervisors, Trisha and Tales, for your guidance, encouragement, and invaluable feedback throughout this process. Your insights not only strengthened this work but gave me courage when I needed it most.

To my family in Colombia, who never doubted my ideas and have always supported me unconditionally: thank you for your unwavering love and for teaching me to follow my heart. You have always supported me, and this is our reward. I would like to thank my friends, who always showed smiles to me, who walk this walk with me and who gave me *muchos ánimos* when I needed them.

Finally, I want to thank myself. Writing this thesis has been one of the greatest challenges and achievements of my life so far, and I am proud of having accomplished it. It was not easy but at the end I made it.

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Executive Summary

This thesis examines Colombian community networks (CNs) as collectively governed internet infrastructures through the theoretical frameworks of the commons, internet sovereignty, and self-determination. Despite the rapid global expansion of internet access, significant gaps persist. Commercial Internet Service Providers (ISPs) often neglect these regions due to low profitability, prompting communities to develop their own connectivity solutions.

Grounded in qualitative case studies of seven Colombian CNs, this research explores their motivations, governance mechanisms, and social dynamics. Using Ostrom's commons as an analytical lens, the study reveals that Colombian CNs align strongly with key principles such as clearly defined boundaries, collective-choice arrangements, and multi-level participation. Beyond providing connectivity, CNs are based on and foster autonomy, cultural identity, and social cohesion. However, challenges remain: declining community participation, reliance on corporate backbone infrastructure, limited technical expertise, and insufficient regulatory recognition threaten their sustainability.

The findings highlight the transformative potential of CNs as infrastructures of autonomy and digital sovereignty. Yet, achieving their long-term viability requires tailored state support, including regulatory frameworks, dedicated funding, and capacity-building programs that respect community autonomy. This research contributes a Global South perspective to ongoing debates on digital inclusion, arguing that CNs represent both a practical solution for bridging the digital divide and a laboratory for reimagining participatory internet governance.

Introduction

The internet has become indispensable to modern life, yet billions remain unconnected. Despite rapid advances in digital technologies and their transformative potential, many users take internet access for granted, often only noticing its absence. While public discussions focus on the latest AI text generators or AI-generated images used as propaganda during elections, approximately 2.6 billion people worldwide remain offline (ITU, 2024).

This digital divide is particularly evident between high-income countries, where 93% of the population has internet access, and low-income countries, where only 27% are connected (ITU, 2023). In Colombia, nearly one in five people lack internet access, with rural areas especially affected, where 68% of rural households remain offline (Botero, 2023; DANE, 2023).

In those areas, traditional commercial internet service providers (ISPs) have little to no incentive to build telecommunication infrastructure because achieving economies of scale is challenging (Lertsinsrubtavee et al., 2015; Braem et al., 2013). This is worrying because the unequal internet access could aggravate unbalanced power relations (Belli, 2017).

In the public discourse, it has been said that access to the internet has the potential to improve social outcomes for people in terms of education, employment, governance, and civic engagement (Callahan et al., 2020; Jaeger et al., 2012). Similarly, the United Nations Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Opinion and Expression highlighted the internet's transformative power for disadvantaged groups by expanding access to information, public debate, and tools to challenge inequality (La Rue, 2011). Reflecting this, the U.N. has incorporated universal and affordable internet access as a key target in its Sustainable Development Goals, particularly for least developed countries (United Nations, n.d.).

To bridge the connectivity gap, major technology companies like Meta, Alphabet, and Starlink have intensified efforts to expand infrastructure globally. Starlink is deploying satellite constellations to reach remote regions, while Google experiments with laser-based technologies to deliver high-speed internet (Moises, 2023; Pultarova et al., 2022). However, as Ávila Pinto (2018) notes, these

corporations often offer critical infrastructure in exchange for citizens' personal data and exposure to targeted advertising.

This growing dominance of big tech raises concerns about service affordability, environmental impact, information manipulation, pervasive surveillance, discriminatory pricing, and threats to net neutrality (De Filippi & Tréguer, 2015; Mies, 2014). These risks are intensified in contexts where governments and local actors cannot compete with the technological and financial advantages of global corporations (Ávila Pinto, 2018), leaving those as the only option for users to access to the internet.

Adding to this, there is increasing concentration in network infrastructures controlled by a few centralized ISPs (De Filippi & Tréguer, 2015). In Colombia, although around 3,000 providers exist (MinTIC, 2022b), two companies accounted for 60% of internet accesses in 2021: the private company Comcel S.A. held 38% of fixed connections, followed by the public company UNE EMP with 20% (MinTIC, 2022a).

Providing sustainable, affordable, and high-quality internet access to all remains a challenge. One promising solution is the model of community networks (CNs), self-operated, citizen-built infrastructures that extend connectivity to underserved areas (Braem et al., 2013). CNs present an alternative to centralized systems dominated by large private corporations (De Filippi & Tréguer, 2015). Although the exact number of community networks operating globally and within Colombia is unclear, at least fifteen active CNs have been identified in Colombia by the civil society organization Colnodo's initiative Redes Comunitarias.

Community networks have existed for over two decades, gaining increasing visibility in recent years through global conversations on universal connectivity and grassroots digital inclusion. Efforts by the U.N. Internet Governance Forum (IGF), the Dynamic Coalition on Community Connectivity (DC3) and organizations like the Internet Society have raised awareness of CNs' potential (Belli, 2018).

Within academia, there is a growing body of research on community networks, often focusing on technical and infrastructural aspects. However, non-technical dimensions, especially governance, social organization, and community participation, remain underexplored (Navarro, Freitag, Baig Viñas, et al.,

2016). Furthermore, relatively few studies adopt a commons perspective, leaving this critical dimension insufficiently addressed, especially from the Global South perspective.

This study uses the commons framework, and self-governance and digital sovereignty ideas, as the lens for analyzing Colombian CNs. Grounded in qualitative case studies of seven diverse community networks, this research tests and expands commons theory in empirical settings.

By centering the voices of those who build and sustain CNs, this research develops an analytical framework linking collective governance practices with existing commons theories. In doing so, it contributes to broader debates on digital infrastructure governance and grassroots connectivity initiatives. Ultimately, this study provides a locally grounded contribution from the Global South to ongoing discussions on internet governance, digital sovereignty, and inclusive, autonomous connectivity models.

With all of this, this research asks: To what extent can community networks in Colombia be understood as commons, and how are they governed as such? Sub-questions guiding this study include: What motivates communities to establish these networks in diverse Colombian contexts? Which governance methods are employed, and how do community members participate in decision-making, maintenance, and rule enforcement? To what extent do these practices align with Ostrom's design principles for managing commons? What challenges do CNs face in sustaining collective action and infrastructure?

Chapter 1: Community networks as subject of study

This section provides an explanation of the research on community networks, their definition and key characteristics. The structure starts with the definition of community networks, and a detailed discussion of their technical and normative characteristics, based on an academic literature review.

After that, a historical overview, literature review, and mapping of key initiatives related to CNs will be presented. This section identifies major actors, highlights funding mechanisms, and lists representative examples across different global contexts. This chapter will conclude with an overview of research on CNs in Latin America, with a particular focus on Colombia, in order to situate this study and highlight the research gaps identified.

1.1. How can community networks be defined?

Community networks are a service that provides basic internet access, typically operated by nonprofit and volunteer-based organizations, and serving a specific geographic region (Keenan & Mitchell Trotter, 1999). These types of services can also be called wireless networks, freenet, redes libres, bottom-up internet infrastructure, grassroots internet, Do-It-Yourself Internet Service Providers, and mesh networks. They may change name or type depending on their structure or purpose.

A definition of community networks that encompasses some of the characteristics is brought by the UN IGF Dynamic Coalition on Community Connectivity (DC3). In 2016, DC3 was organized by the United Nations as a global multi-stakeholder platform, highlighting the potential of CNs to foster sustainable internet access while enabling fundamental rights like freedom of expression and self-determination (IGF, n.d.). Through inputs, open consultations, comments, and feedback, the Declaration on Community Connectivity was published between 2016 and 2017, defining CNs as:

“Structured to be open, free, and to respect network neutrality. Such networks rely on the active participation of local communities in the design, development, deployment, and management of shared infrastructure as a common resource, owned by the community, and operated in a democratic fashion. Community networks can be operationalised, wholly or partly, through individuals and local stakeholders, NGO’s, private sector entities, and/or public administrations,” (Belli, 2017a, p. 238).

Unbundling this definition, CNs are *open* because anyone can know how they are built and join the infrastructure. They are open in terms of usage of the infrastructure and participation in developing the network, including governance, maintenance, operation and construction (Baig et al, 2015). CNs are *free* due to their principle of non-discrimination in access, meaning that they should be accessible for the participants to join, some of the networks have very low costs of access while others can be free of charge for the participants. However, there are cases where the CNs have developed business models to try to be sustainable (Gwaka et al, 2023). Community networks are *neutral* because they can transmit any type of data for any purpose, any technical solution can be used to extend them and they respect net neutrality (Baig et al., 2015).

In addition, issues like governance and ownership are decentralized. CNs are self-owned and self-managed by the participants, stimulating growth in capacity and services (Braem et al., 2013). Rather than profiting, CNs focus on the actual needs of the community (De Filippi & Tréguer, 2015). To expand and maintain CNs, different factors influence: technological capabilities of the participants, existence of local organizations, availability of natural and financial resources, environmental and climate-related conditions, regulatory frameworks, and the existence of institutions supporting them, among others (Baca et al., 2018).

1.2. Technical and economic characteristics

From a technical standpoint, CNs are large-scale, decentralized systems composed of numerous nodes, links, content servers, mesh structures, and services, integrating a mix of wired, wireless, and fiber-optic connections with diverse routing schemes (Braem et al., 2013). Community networks typically rely on low-cost Wi-Fi

equipment based on the IEEE 802.11 family of standards and primarily operate within the unlicensed 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz spectrum bands.

This is explained by the fact that licensed spectrum bands are generally reserved for entities with exclusive rights, such as commercial operators or governmental entities. By contrast, regulatory frameworks in many countries permit unlicensed use of certain bands, facilitating the deployment of CNs without the need of costly licenses (Belli et al., 2016; Gwaka et al., 2023).

In this way, depending on factors such as geography, costs, state infrastructure and regulations, community networks can use and mix mesh, hotspots, free and libre open software, Television White Space (TVWS) or unlicensed technologies to build the infrastructure of the network (Gwaka et al., 2023). For example, the Southern California Tribal Digital Village initiative provides connectivity through broadband wireless, TVWS, and fiber (Yoo et al., 2021).

Even when using different types, the technology and infrastructure in CNs may face challenges in terms of transmission quality or speed. Bandwidth may not be sufficient for the transmission of high-definition multimedia content and real-time applications, and it is prone to interference and congestion, which can severely degrade the quality of service (Zhao et al., 2017). In some cases excessive device connections could lead to network congestion, reducing bandwidth availability and quality for other participants (Damsgaard et al., 2006). However, Belli et al. (2016) emphasize that participants in CNs may be able and willing to develop technologies that have even higher performance than the commercial vendors.

Some CNs use technologies that are open source, with the goal of spreading free access to them, as well as promoting the transfer of knowledge to maintain and expand the infrastructure and coverage (Saldana et al., 2017). Community networks must balance openness and transparency in infrastructure and governance with respect for data privacy. It is desirable for users to have the capacity to engage with the network while preserving their privacy and that of the data they transmit (Braem et al., 2013).

Furthermore, community networks rely on less expensive hardware, which in turn reduces operational expenses and facilitates their democratization (Braem et al., 2013; Gwaka et al., 2023). However, there are still costs that need to be covered. For

instance, the deployment of TakNet in Thailand required approximately \$1,200 USD to cover hardware and other miscellaneous expenses plus a monthly ADSL subscription fee of \$28 USD, that was shared among the villagers (Lertsinsruttavee et al., 2015).

In addition, operation of telecommunications infrastructure entails additional expenses, including those associated with the electrical infrastructure necessary for network power, as well as the physical locations for the placement of machinery and cables. Some networks are established in accessible public facilities such as parks, schools, libraries, hospitals, and other community-centric locations. However, this approach may potentially lead to inequalities in access and distribution due to the existing uneven distribution of hospitals and schools in rural and underserved regions (Gwaka et al., 2023).

As mentioned, CNs are established primarily to provide services to communities with limited resources. To do this, it is necessary to generate revenue to cover the operation and maintenance of the network. In some cases, these networks need to develop business models to ensure financial sustainability. CNs collect resources from providing services, not infrastructure, in contrast to mainstream corporate internet providers that base their business on controlling infrastructure (Saldana et al., 2016).

Gwaka et al. (2023) studied twenty-one CNs, and found out that 67% of them have developed revenue-generating business models. They highlighted the case of the Zenzeleni Network in South Africa, which has shown a successful model, while the Balsapuerto Network in Peru encountered a temporary disruption due to a lack of financial resources, which can be attributed to the network's failure to incorporate a business model (Gwaka et al., 2023).

As mentioned before it is impossible to know all the active CNs in the world, nonetheless, some have a notable reach, for example, Guifi.net in Spain with almost 40 thousand working nodes (Guifi.Net, n.d.), and FunkFeuer with more than 220 nodes in Vienna. Some other well-known examples are B4RN24, in the U.K.; Zenzeleni Networks (Mankosi CWN) in South Africa; TakNET in Thailand; AlterMundi, in Argentina; Nepal Wireless Networking Project (NWNP); and Mesh Bukavu, which also runs a community radio station in the Democratic Republic of

Congo (Baig et al., 2015; Belli, 2016, 2018; Braem et al., 2013; Navarro et al., 2016). In Colombia, with the support of the Colombian NGO Colnodo, at least fifteen CNs have been developed in different regions of the country, offering diverse services and connecting communities to the internet.

To get a broad, though now outdated, overview of CNs, one can refer to a 2016 report produced by the Network Infrastructure as Commons project, co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme. Navarro et al. (2016) compiled an extensive list of CNs, primarily in Europe but also including initiatives from other parts of the world. The report catalogued both active and inactive networks, and in some cases, provided additional details such as years of operation, number of nodes, users, and participants. However, given that nearly a decade has passed since its publication, the accuracy and relevance of the data may now be limited.

1.3. Normative characteristics of community networks

1.3.1. Goals and motivations

To a certain extent, the objectives of CNs go beyond mere access to the internet and the solution to the digital divide; CNs aim at engaging and empowering community members to become new active participants in the internet, contributing to its development from the bottom up (Belli, 2016; Belli et al., 2016). CNs frequently aspire to expand access to the internet and to educate individuals and the community about it (Keenan & Mitchell Trotter, 1999).

Some CNs have demonstrated their support for digital literacy, freedom of expression, innovation, capacity-building, and the expansion of internet infrastructure (Belli et al., 2016). However, establishing a clear correlation between connectivity through CNs and the preservation of values and respect for human rights may be challenging to demonstrate.

CNs are also regarded as a means for civil society to regain control over the communication infrastructure. By acquiring the technological know-how to be autonomous in their communication, individuals and groups can avoid being dependent on third parties, which are usually large corporations (De Filippi & Tréguer, 2015). The active involvement of community members in this process has

shown to engender beneficial effects, including the promotion of the local economy, as well as digital inclusion (Belli et al., 2016).

In this context, the concept of inverse infrastructure emerges, signifying the potential of user-driven, decentralized, and self-managed technology as an alternative to the dominant top-down model (Crabu & Magaudda, 2018). Inverse infrastructure initiatives are typically driven by reciprocity and non-financial self-interest (Egyedi & Vree, 2012). To keep the infrastructure running, openness plays a fundamental role in terms of technical issues, markets, institutions, and political sense (Egyedi & Vree, 2012).

As just mentioned, the literature says that CNs directly engage users who can be active participants in the network design, deployment, operation, and maintenance (Belli et al., 2016). In this way participants should be able to understand how the network works in technical terms and social norms, and even in some cases how to provide additional services and content to the network (Belli, 2016).

In CNs, users or customers actively participate in the role of operators, owners, governors, and maintainers of the network. This dynamic fosters not only connectivity but also the expansion of its use. Furthermore, it could facilitate the establishment of cooperative relations, potentially generating social, technical, and economic innovations (Belli et al., 2016).

However, CNs also present contradictions and challenges. Fuchs (2017) highlights concerns regarding their long-term sustainability, including issues such as e-waste generation and increased energy consumption. Even, in some cases, according to him, while CNs may reduce the digital divide, they risk reinforcing a form of second-class internet access, offering limited or inferior services compared to those provided by mainstream commercial providers.

Nevertheless, CNs aim not just to address both technical issues, such as improving access, but also they have social goals, including fostering social cohesion and raising political awareness about internet-related matters (Saldana et al., 2016). The identified objectives include providing affordable access to underserved areas, reducing initial capital expenditures, promoting expertise and innovation, lowering barriers to internet adoption—such as improving digital literacy—, strengthening

community building and quality of life, experimenting with alternative governance and ownership models, recognizing network infrastructures as a commons, and stimulating political debates on topics like net neutrality and knowledge sharing (Saldana et al., 2016). These motivations are relevant in the current context shaped by capitalism, surveillance, censorship, authoritarian practices, platform monopolies, overprotection of intellectual property, political constraints and corporate enclosure (Dulong de Rosnay & Stalder, 2020; Levine, 2007).

In this sense, it is imperative to acknowledge that the motivations underlying participation in the development and maintenance of networks may vary depending on the context, the needs, and the personal interests of the participants. In the context of open and horizontal governance models, for instance, there may be altruistic intentions to promote the free sharing of connectivity, but also more personal desires of growth and acquiring experience and expertise (Saldana et al., 2016).

1.3.2. Participation

According to the literature about CNs, it is crucial to recognize that all members of community networks should be seen as active participants. They have the right and freedom to join and use the network for any purpose, as long as they maintain its integrity, respect other participants, and adhere to the principles of net neutrality (Belli, 2016). CNs aim to empower community members to become not only users but also contributors to the internet, promoting digital inclusion and driving the continuous evolution of the network (Belli, 2017b).

However, since participants have that liberty, they may choose to use the network without actively participating or contributing to its development. In some cases, conflicts may arise between the individual intentions of community members and the collective interests of the group utilizing the network. Damsgaard et al. (2006) highlighted the risk of network contamination, such as the unnecessary addition of passwords or the excessive consumption of bandwidth (finite) for trivial purposes, both of which can negatively impact other users' access and experience. To avoid these kinds of conflicts, CNs usually have their own governance structures and protocols to solve conflicts.

Participants may vary in profile, characteristics, demographics, and motivations. The stakeholders involved in CNs may include i) *volunteers* interested in issues such as neutrality, innovation, and privacy; ii) *professionals* focused on demand, supply, and operations; iii) *customers* that use the network; and iv) *public administrators* interested in regulating the use of public space and participation in society (Baig et al., 2015; Belli, 2016).

As seen, stakeholders within CNs are a heterogeneous group, with different profiles and roles. In terms of tasks, there are many ways in which community members can participate, including the provision of humanpower, provision of security, management and maintenance of technical issues, and governance (Belli et al., 2016; Gwaka et al., 2023).

The diversity of participants' profiles is crucial for the development and establishment of the network. The active involvement of minority groups and individuals—often overlooked by the private sector or public administrators—can significantly enhance the network's growth and sustainability. For instance, Gwaka et al. (2023) emphasized the positive impact of women's involvement in promoting safer spaces and reducing the gender gap within the community. When women are actively engaged in the management and governance of the network, it can create additional benefits for other women in the community, improving their access to the internet and fostering a more meaningful connectivity.

On the contrary, Bidwell (2019) has shown how the physical and social spaces in which CNs are located and in which learning processes take place can contribute to gender exclusion and even increase inequalities between women and men. Although in some cases women hold leadership positions in CNs, their participation in decision-making could remain minimal, as seen in Mexico, India, and Indonesia, where men dominate discussions, decisions, and training processes. In many cases, women are excluded from meetings, dismissed as lacking knowledge, or forced to avoid meetings due to the time commitment required. This is the case of a CN in Mexico, where the indigenous assembly has a woman president, but only two other women were present among 75 men at the meetings (Bidwell, 2019).

1.3.3. Alliances and partnerships

Another characteristic found in CNs is the ability and need to consolidate alliances. Part of the reason why community networks survive and prosper is their ability to form partnerships with businesses, governments, educational institutions, individuals and other participants (Keenan & Mitchell Trotter, 1999). Some researchers have highlighted the role of organizations such as the Internet Society (ISOC) and the Association for Progressive Communications (APC) in providing financial and technical support. In their study, Gwaka et al. (2023) found that 90% of the CNs interviewed received funding from governments and NGOs, while only 14% obtained contributions from community members.

As an example of that, ISOC has a program called "Connecting the unconnected" that provides financial support to community and local organizations in their efforts to develop and expand internet access solutions, with the goal of addressing the digital divide in rural, remote, and low-income areas (ISOC, n.d.). In 2025, the funding allocated for the creation of new infrastructure is between \$15,000 and \$40,000 USD, while the funding allocated for the expansion or enhancement of existing access solutions falls between \$5,000 and \$20,000 USD (ISOC, n.d.).

Although partnerships can be beneficial for community networks, they can also pose challenges related to autonomy and independence. Reliance on a few dominant partners carries the risk that a single actor could shape the priorities and steer the development of projects (Gwaka et al., 2023).

In some cases, the strong influence of external stakeholders can even affect the decision-making processes involved in the governance of CNs, especially at the beginning of the initiative while members are being trained to manage the network. In their study, Gwaka et al. (2023) found that only 38% of the CNs surveyed had community members making key decisions, and only 10% had structured decision-making processes involving local as well as external parties.

1.4. Community networks in Latin America and Colombia

Much of the academic literature on CNs has concentrated on large-scale initiatives in the Global North. However, Latin America offers a particularly rich

context for analysis. As Baladron (2021) notes, CNs on Latin America not only address the lack of connectivity but also confront the persistent inequalities affecting Indigenous peoples, rural populations, residents of small villages, women, and other marginalized groups.

From an academic point of view, the work of Luca Belli (2016, 2017a) and other scholars from the FGV Direito Rio - Escola de Direito do Rio de Janeiro, in Brazil, can be highlighted. In the publications *Community Networks, the Internet by the People, for the People* (Belli, 2017a) and *Community Connectivity: Building the internet from Scratch* (Belli, 2016), the authors researched case studies in Mexico, Brazil, Argentina, and Venezuela. Other articles have researched different networks such as Altermundi in Argentina and the creation of the open hardware to provide internet Libre Router (Baladron, 2021; Prato et al., 2022).

Additionally, from a sociological perspective, Rosa (2023) examined how the community values of the Tseltal and Zapoteco pueblos in Mexico are supported by the network they built. From the senses of internet governance, Rosa highlights specific initiatives that demonstrate the pervasive influence of *comunalidad* values within networks, offering evidence of a pluriversal and decolonial perspective.

In Colombia, the focus of some of the articles and case studies has been on more technical issues or the regulation of CNs (Gómez & Osorio, 2016). These studies have noted that CNs do not only provide internet connectivity but also offer additional services such as hosting informative websites and instant communication services. Some activists see how CNs in Colombia became political actors through advocacy, as well as through communication initiatives to gain legitimacy in the public sphere (Botero Cabrera & Saavedra Rionda, 2021).

One of the results of this advocacy process is Decree 1079 of 2023, in which the Presidency recognizes the importance of local community internet providers in combating the digital divide. The decree establishes the legal conditions for the provision of community fixed internet services, such as the limit of 3000 access points per network and the non-profit nature of the service (MinTIC & Presidencia de Colombia, 2023). Despite the growing global scholarship on CNs, research focusing specifically on Colombia is scarce, and studies framed within internet governance or commons-based approaches are notably absent.

Chapter 2: Commons, self-sovereignty and internet governance

Because community networks are collectively owned and managed, neither governed by market logic nor treated as conventional public resources, they are well-suited to analysis through the lens of the commons framework. This chapter first introduces the concept of the commons and outlines its key characteristics, drawing particularly on Elinor Ostrom's and other scholars' work on common-pool resources (CPRs) as a central analytical lens. Then, the second section situates this discussion within broader debates on internet governance, and self-sovereignty. Finally, the third section applies these theoretical insights to the literature on community networks, framing them as collectively managed infrastructure commons. Together, these sections establish the conceptual foundation for analyzing Colombian CNs as participatory and self-governed forms of internet infrastructure.

2.1 The commons framework

To understand the framework of the commons, it is needed to start from its beginning as a subject of study. In her book *Governing the Commons*, Ostrom (1990) posits that there is an alternative to the state and the market for governing natural resources in order to prevent their destruction. She analyzes successful and unsuccessful efforts by individuals to collaborate and create institutions to manage resources (Ostrom, 1990).

Ostrom examines and questionnates three influential models: Hardin's *Tragedy of the Commons*—which will be discussed in more detail later in this section—, the *Prisoner's Dilemma*, and Mancur Olson's *Logic of Collective Action*. These models suggest that without external enforcement, individuals are unlikely to cooperate and achieve collective benefits (Ostrom, 1990). In response, Ostrom introduces the commons as an alternative model, grounded in empirical evidence, which she argues demonstrates that self-governance can be both viable and effective.

That way, commons refers to a community that shares resources and collectively governs them as well as the processes of access and reproduction,

through horizontal practices of commoning (De Angelis, 2017). David Boiller (2014, as cited in Bauwens et al., 2019) characterizes commons as a shared resource, co-governed by its user community according to the rules and norms of that community. The commons are seen as a contribution to the common good, fighting consumerism and passive citizenship, and as beneficial to civil society and democracy (Hess & Ostrom, 2007).

Commons and commons-based peer production are often seen as alternative models to capitalist forms of production (Birkinbine, 2018). Indeed, commons can be interpreted as the opposite of private property, in the sense that in commons there is not a single powerful person who owns and has control over the use of and access to the resources. Here, the resources can be accessed and used by anyone among a group of people who follow a set of rules (Benkler, 2006). Nevertheless, power in some commons based movements is still somewhat ambiguous, especially in terms of unanticipated or unwanted uses of the resources (Birkinbine, 2018).

It can be said that the term commons does not refer to the resources, the community, or a specific place. Instead, it refers to the institutional arrangement of these elements (Frischmann et al., 2014). This notion is the fundamental premise for the present research.

Even so, one of the criticisms of commons management is the belief that it is inherently unsustainable, as individuals are likely to prioritize personal gain, leading to the overexploitation of shared resources (Birkinbine, 2018). That is known as the myth of the tragedy of the commons, and it is often cited when talking about collective management of resources (Fuster Morell, 2010).

Garrett Hardin published an essay in 1968 arguing that individuals are locked into a system that forces them to increase their utility indefinitely in a world of limited resources. He claims that a single person can benefit from the common resource and use it indefinitely, thus limiting the general use or access of the other members (Hardin, 1968). His main point is that if people shared resources without external control, they would overuse them. He suggests that government regulation and privatization can solve the problem, by being in charge of the resources, allocating the right to enter or access them (Frischmann, 2013).

Hardin's essay was widely recognised and read, reflecting the prevailing morality of his time and context (Nijhuis, 2021). For decades, economists, particularly those who adhere to classical and neoliberal economic principles, have claimed that any form of collective resource management system is destined to collapse (Fuster Morell, 2010). However, the works of Elinor Ostrom (1990, 2015), Hess (2007), Benkler (2006), Lessig (2004) and a wide range of other scholars challenge his assumptions.

Here it is important to understand that the commons is not immune to flaws or criticism. Individual actions can unintentionally harm the group, particularly when personal interests clash with collective goals. An action that seems reasonable or beneficial for an individual may have negative consequences for the wider community (Damsgaard et al., 2006).

But it is in this scenery where context and social norms play a fundamental role, shaping people's behaviours to superpose community's interests over personal immediate interests (Weinstein, 2013). In this way, the commons work under social norms, rules, and legal mechanisms that allow communities to share ownership and manage resources collectively (Bollier, 2007).

A commons develops around a resource, called a *common-pool resource* (CPR). It is defined by Ostrom as “a natural or [hu]man-made resource system that is sufficiently large as to make it costly (but not impossible) to exclude potential beneficiaries from obtaining benefits from its use” (Ostrom, 1990, p. 30). CPRs can be natural resources and inherited—like land, forests or water—or created by people—such as knowledge, ideas, culture, free software or, in this case, network infrastructure (Bauwens et al., 2019).

Ostrom (1990) distinguishes between resource systems—such as forests, fisheries, or irrigation canals—, and resource units, which are the specific goods individuals extract from those systems—like timber, fish, or water. A resource system can be thought of as a stock—such as fish population, or groundwater reserve—that has the potential to produce a regular flow of valuable goods or services. While resource units are individually appropriated, they all come from a shared system.

Following commons principle and under optimal or sustainable conditions, the flow of the resource can be maintained over time without depleting the

underlying stock or damaging the broader system that supports it (Ostrom, 1990). In other words, the resource can be used continuously as long as it is managed in a way that keeps the stock and the system healthy. CPR models propose that when properly managed, they maximize efficiency of the resources and ensure long-term sustainability (Navarro, Freitag, Dimogerontakis, et al., 2016)

In this context, the terms *excludability* and *rivalry* are frequently encountered. Excludability refers to the degree to which access to a resource can be restricted. A highly excludable resource is typically considered private property, as the owner possesses the authority to prevent others from using it. In contrast to that, a resource with low excludability is more aligned with common property, where access is shared among a broader group of users (Birkinbine, 2018).

In the same line, commons can refer to either rivalrous resources or non-rival resources. Rivalry, in this context, signifies the degree to which the utilization of a resource by one individual hinders the capacity of another to use the same resource. In essence, this concept implies that two individuals cannot have or use the same resource at the same time (Birkinbine, 2018). Here, what the commons proposes is that self-regulation can promote sustainability and adaptability as well as preventing congestion or overuse (Navarro, Freitag, Dimogerontakis, et al., 2016).

2.1.1. Characteristics of commons and governance

In her framework, Ostrom proposes that individuals have two alternatives: continue with the status quo rules or support a change in the station quo rules (Ostrom, 1990). Here, context plays a fundamental factor in the decision to change the rules and in terms of governing the CPRs. For example, how close or far administrative offices are located from the CPR would affect the autonomy of the individuals in making their own rules. In the same way, what is allowed and forbidden by central authorities could affect the processes.

Commons share several key characteristics. They are typically bounded at a local to regional scale, and the communities that use and manage them usually range from a few dozen to a few thousand members. The appropriators often share a common interest in maintaining and preserving the resource for long-term use. They also tend to have a shared cultural and institutional background, which supports

cooperation. Management of commons often relies on empirical experience, where learning through trial and error is a practical approach (Stern, 2011).

The commons are about governance and their analysis involves the rules, decisions and behaviours collectively made (Ostrom & Hess, 2007). In this way, effective mechanisms of governance are fundamental to maintain CPRs in the long run and in a sustainable way (Belli et al., 2016). Ostrom identified eight design principles that should be present in the governance of commons (Ostrom, 1990; Dulong de Rosnay & Stalder, 2020; Hess & Ostrom, 2007; Nijhuis, 2021; Weinstein, 2013):

1. Clear defined community boundaries, designed by the community on how to withdraw resource units.
2. Correlation between appropriation and provision rule and local conditions. The rules need to be well-matched to local needs and context.
3. Collective choice arrangements. Participatory decision-making processes and the possibility for the participants to modify the rules.
4. Effective monitoring, accountability, and moderation.
5. Graduated sanctions mechanisms for rule-breakers, depending on the seriousness and the context of the offense.
6. Conflict resolution mechanisms, low-cost and accessible for the members.
7. The right to organize themselves and be recognized by authorities. Community members have the right to make their own rules and have them respected by outside authorities.
8. Nested enterprises, with governance layered or multi-level system of governance for managing commons. Having operational rules (day-to-day), collective choice rules and constitutional rules.

Even with the detailed analysis by Ostrom and her collaborators on the common elements and rule-based systems governing the commons, critiques remain regarding the limitations of their framework. Weinstein (2013) for instance, highlighted its insufficient attention to the political power relations embedded within

these governance structures. While Ostrom's work emphasizes on collective self-organization, it tends to overlook how power asymmetries related to class, gender, or access to decision-making mechanisms shape who participates, who benefits, and who is excluded from commons governance.

2.1.2. Different applications of the commons framework

The commons perspective has had many interpretations and applications over time, such as the knowledge commons (Hess & Ostrom, 2007), spectrum commons (Benkler, 2012) and infrastructure commons (Frischmann, 2007, 2012). For example, Frischmann (2007, 2012) highlights the role of commons management of open accessible infrastructures in generating value for users and points out that basic infrastructure contributes to social and public goods.

In the same way, the term digital commons is used to describe a subset of the commons where the resources consist of knowledge, information, data and culture, and are created and/or maintained online (Dulong de Rosnay & Stalder, 2020). The question of whether digital resources should be considered commons is currently a topic of debate that has been ongoing for many years.

Unlike other commons that may suffer from overuse or physical scarcity, digital commons are not inherently limited by material constraints. However, they remain vulnerable to a range of other challenges, such as discrimination, insufficient resources, legal restrictions, and even forms of digital pollution (Dulong de Rosnay & Stalder, 2020).

Along the same lines, it is valuable to keep in mind some discussions around digital commons. On one hand, communities engaged in creating and maintaining digital commons require a progressive political project that goes beyond merely defending commons-based resources against enclosure. This project should actively incorporate resources from the state and capital into the commons' circuits (Birkinbine, 2018). The relationship between the commons, private and public goods, and the management of resources is a topic of discussion in terms of sovereignty and raises questions about sustainability and the interplay of private and public interests.

On the other hand, discussions about referring to the internet as a commons remain valid. Raymond (2013) argues that the internet should not be considered a commons because it is non-rival and excludable, given the existence of various forms of exclusion. The aforementioned data on the lack of connectivity and differences in internet coverage are proof of that. Others would say that the internet is not a commons because it is controlled as private property by giant monopolists such as Microsoft, Apple, Google, Amazon, Facebook and a few other players (Mies, 2014).

In spite of it, there are scholars who argue that digital resources and infrastructure can be considered commons. For example, Levine (2007) says that the internet was born as a libertarian commons and that it allows citizens to contribute to collective action and civic engagement. From a critical perspective, Fuchs argues that the internet as it is known today is based on the capitalist exploitation of users' data. Still he suggests that it should be managed and owned collectively through self-organisation (Fuchs, 2008).

As said before, understanding the internet and digital resources as commons is a contested idea. In the case of this research, internet infrastructure developed as community networks could be considered as commons. More than what the internet is used for (digital and knowledge commons), the focus here is on the social and political arrangements communities have to collectively provide and maintain internet infrastructure in their communities.

Managing infrastructure as a commons promotes openness and aims to combat discrimination against both users and uses of the resource, reducing dependence on market-driven decisions and government-controlled dynamics (Frischmann, 2012). In addition, basic infrastructure can be seen as a contribution to social fabric and public goods where end-users build, develop, produce and distribute public and non-market goods (Frischmann, 2007).

2.2 Internet governance, self-sovereignty and self-determination

The commons and community networks can be framed in academic and political discussions of internet governance, sovereignty, and self-determination. The

question of how to govern the internet has been examined from a range of academic perspectives. Internet governance encompasses the design and management of the technologies and infrastructures that enable the internet to function effectively (Denardis, 2014). Research in this field focuses not only on the technical architecture of the internet and public and private actors that exert control over it, but also on the policies that guide its evolution or that restrain it.

In addition, there is an interest in analyzing how governance structures themselves function as mechanisms of power and control. The internet is made of interconnected networks that reflect and produce power relations within and over networks. Scholars have examined how different actors shape these dynamics, with Pohle and Voelsen (2022) analyzing the effects of centralization and power concentration on internet structures. While there may be broad consensus on preserving the technical underpinnings of the global internet, more authoritarian models of governance continue to expand within subnetworks, potentially reshaping the overall structure of the internet (Pohle & Voelsen, 2022). Both private companies and certain states have actively worked to centralize control within and over these networks.

To gain and maintain power, governments have employed the concept of *digital sovereignty* in political discourse as a means of asserting authority over the internet, thereby countering broader demands for *self-determination* (Pohle & Thiel, 2020). Although the term digital sovereignty dates back to the decade of 1990, it began to gain prominence following Edward Snowden's revelations about the widespread global surveillance practices conducted by U.S. intelligence agencies and their allies (Pohle et al., 2024; Pohle & Voelsen, 2022). Since then its legal and political meaning have been linked to the authority of states over the internet allegedly to protect citizens, institutions and companies (Musiani, 2022).

However, within the realm of digital sovereignty, the dominant, policy-driven and state-centric interpretations of sovereignty are challenged. Control over infrastructure, data, and protocols is not held exclusively by states; it sometimes resides with private corporations, particularly huge tech companies, and it is challenged and contested by individuals and communities (Couture & Toupin, 2019).

As different actors pursue their own visions of digital sovereignty, multiple conceptions can overlap or collide within the same domain (Jiang & Belli, 2025). Belli (2024) brought the notion of Good Digital Sovereignty, referring to the possibility to understand technology and use it for their own benefit; and Calderón Beltrán (2016) defined it as a form of independence and empowerment, to be used as an anti-establishment practice.

According to Couture and Toupin (2019) the notion of sovereignty can be applied to the digital sphere by identifying five perspectives: Cyberspace; Digital Governments and States; Indigenous; Personal; and Social Movements Digital Sovereignty (Couture & Toupin, 2019). The latter can be found in commons-based governance movements such as Free/Libre and Open-Source Software (FOSS) and Creative Commons (De Filippi & Tréguer, 2015). The Social Movements Digital Sovereignty approach supports the autonomy of social movements by giving them collective control over the technology and digital infrastructure, empowering them to create, design and use tools that are customized to meet their specific needs (Couture & Toupin, 2019).

What is crucial here is the recognition that infrastructures—and the practices surrounding their use—actively shape and structure social realities (Musiani, 2022). Civil society actors and social movements engaging with technological sovereignty are often driven by the dual aim of meeting immediate community needs while fostering broader political and social transformation (Couture & Toupin, 2019; Haché, 2014). In this context, the pursuit of technological sovereignty in information technologies represents an effort to challenge and resist established power structures, seeking emancipation from forms of technological dependency and digital imperialism (Calderón Beltrán, 2016).

In this way, digital and technological sovereignty refer not only to states and governments, but to people exercising their agency and authority over data, software, hardware, and infrastructure. In other words, digital sovereignty refers to the possibility of enjoying the right to self-determination (Belli, 2024). With all of these in mind, there is a potential for studying collective self-governance and self-sovereignty at local levels through real cases of CNS.

2.3 Community networks as commons

Applying the characteristics of commons to community networks can lead to a better analysis and understanding of how they work and how they are governed. By definition, community networks are collectively built, owned, and managed by groups of people who come together to do so. In this sense, commons can be a good lens through which to analyze them, as they share the same principles of openness and non-discrimination in access and use of resources. When these principles are applied to infrastructure, the result is a network of collective goods, managed as common-pool resources and socially produced (Navarro, Freitag, Baig Viñas, et al., 2016).

In the same way, community networks are increasingly seen as an alternative for providing internet access, distinct from both private companies and public sector initiatives. In many cases, broadband and wired internet services are delivered through highly concentrated market structures, where a few companies own the infrastructure and exercise significant control over the flow of information (Benkler, 2006). The infrastructure for providing internet services has traditionally been managed first by national telecom monopolies, and later by incumbent telecom providers and other for-profit operators (Navarro, Baig, et al., 2016).

Furthermore, according to the definition of CPR developed by Ostrom (1990), community networks are the human-made resource system and the limited units they offer would be the connectivity that the participants obtain (Navarro, Freitag, Baig Viñas, et al., 2016). However, at applying this principles, it is evident that in internet access, excluding people from access to internet is possible, which is contrary to what Ostrom proposes as CPR.

Historically, and particularly since the wave of telecommunications privatization, access to the internet has been shaped by mechanisms of exclusion and economic extraction. Under commercial models, individuals unable to afford subscription fees are systematically denied connectivity, increasing the number of millions that remain offline due to the absence of market incentives or the failure of the state to ensure universal access. In contrast, CNs seek to disrupt this paradigm by grounding their operation in principles of openness and non-discrimination in both access and use.

While CNs are theoretically non-rivalrous, in practice this requires significant capacity to provide services without exclusion. In the context of internet provision, when many people at the same time are using the network, especially high-data volume applications such as video, streaming, or videogames, issues such as network congestion, reduced speed, and service quality degradation can arise. That is called *subtractability*. Without careful design and strategic planning, infrastructure can become unevenly distributed and overburdened, undermining its effectiveness as a system for delivering connectivity as a consumable resource (Navarro, Freitag, Baig Viñas, et al., 2016).

In addition, due to their non-excludable nature, CNs are vulnerable to the *free-riding problem*. That means that once a network is established and provides internet, it becomes difficult to deny access to individuals within the coverage area, even if they have not contributed to its construction or maintenance. However, CNs are intentionally designed to be non-excludable, embracing openness as a foundational principle (Baig et al., 2015).

To be part of the CN, participants need to accept the rules, they must contribute to the infrastructure and so they own collectively the network. In that sense, probably, there are users and third parties who join the benefits of the network but do not act directly in the government processes, for example, members of the family or people who live in the same house (Navarro, Freitag, Baig Viñas, et al., 2016). However, the physical infrastructure of CNs implies that the nodes make the network stronger and bigger, meaning that even just with adding nodes, individuals participate in the deployment of the network.

One of the principles that CNs share is the collective management and governance of the network, aiming for the democratic participation of its members, equity, gender equality, diversity, and plurality (Baladron, 2021). CNs can be seen as a testing ground for new governance structures that translate the democratic practices of local communities (Belli, 2017a).

To see this in practice, Baig et al. (2015) showed how guifi.net is managed as commons, following principles of collective participation and well-defined governance structures. They also included a stakeholder analysis to identify roles and interests around the CN. In guifi.net, Baig et al. identified seven main groups of

people involved in the network: (1) *volunteers* responsible for installing routers and antennas, laying cables, assisting newcomers, and maintaining technical operations; (2) *professionals* who receive compensation for their services; (3) *the Guifi.net Foundation*, acting as the default operator and promoting network-related projects; (4) *other non-profit organizations*, such as local user associations and cooperatives; (5) *public administrators*, including policymakers and local councils; (6) *universities* that contribute to infrastructure deployment and research; and (7) *third parties*.

2.3.1. Governance mechanisms

Community networks give rise not only to new infrastructure but also to new governance models and new business opportunities that complement and fill the gaps left by the classic internet access provision paradigm (Belli, 2017b). CNs in principle have participatory administration models and non-centralized structures, including members that are users, contributors and owners (Saldana et al., 2016). The self-organization systems encompass the allocation of tasks, such as IP addressing and routing (Saldana et al., 2017).

As well, community networks have the potential to empower citizens within local communities to develop and embed their own democratic practices into the management of the networks that serve them (Belli, 2017b). As CPRs, CNs require effective governance structures to maintain a long-term vision and to manage the challenges that stakeholders and the complex dynamic pose (Navarro, Freitag, Baig Viñas, et al., 2016).

As previously discussed, eight key prerequisites have been identified to ensure the sustainability of CPRs. To illustrate how these principles apply to community networks, the following discussion draws on two key sources: *Guifi.net, a crowdsourced network infrastructure held in common* (Baig et al., 2015) and *A Commons-Oriented Framework for Community Networks* (Navarro, Freitag, Baig Viñas, et al., 2016).

1. **Clear defined boundaries:** They are defined in the governance tools and the legal framework for participation. In the case of guifi.net all participants need to subscribe to the licence, where all the duties, rights and principles are

established. Also, the network management and governance tools are well defined.

2. Correlation between appropriation and provision rules and local conditions: In CNs the rules to access and usage of the network should correlate with its provision and expansion. Tools such as a mapping of the network are useful for this.
3. Collective choice arrangements: The use of communication and governance tools such as mailing lists and face-to-face meetings to make decisions.
4. Effective monitoring: Monitoring is made by members or monitors that are accountable to the members. In the case of guifi.net through network managing and software tools, monitors check the open data about the network and coordinate decisions when it is needed.
5. Graduated sanctions mechanisms: they are included in the conflict resolution mechanisms.
6. Conflict resolution mechanisms: in the case of guifi.net they established three levels of escalation, progressive complexity and cost.
7. Right to be recognized by authorities: Self-determination of the community is recognized by external authorities as well as the governance tools and licenses align with legal frameworks.
8. Nested enterprises: for large networks, complexity makes it necessary to have second-layer organizations having local CPRs as the base and federated CPRs.

2.3.2. Self-determination and sovereignty:

Self-determination in the context of connectivity refers to the capacity of individuals and communities to design, develop, and govern their own network infrastructure autonomously and democratically (Belli, 2017b). It implies both the right and the means to establish communication systems based on the needs and values of the community. This is realized when people freely associate to collectively define, deploy, and maintain digital infrastructure as a common good, thereby exercising their right to seek, receive, and impart information (Belli, 2017a).

Community networks embody this principle by offering alternatives to centralized, market-driven models of internet provision. In response to public policy shortcomings and market failures, many communities have taken initiative to overcome digital exclusion by building their own infrastructure. Through this, they become active agents in shaping their digital futures (Belli, 2018). CNs enable new governance models and socio-economic arrangements, challenging traditional paradigms of internet access and control (Belli, 2017b).

These networks have generated growing interest as potential tools to resist the dominance of corporate internet providers and mitigate the negative effects of centralized control (Lynch, 2021). As Belli (2017b) argues, network self-determination is closely tied to broader social and political empowerment. It not only fosters economic revitalization but also encourages civic participation, potentially contributing to more accountable and responsive local governance.

Importantly, CNs are shaped by local needs, contexts, and priorities. For instance, some communities may initially focus on developing local intranets, networks that support local communication and access to shared information, rather than full internet connectivity (Belli, 2017b). Technological choices, such as using wireless versus wired infrastructure, depend heavily on geographic, regulatory, and economic factors. The variety of topologies, management systems, and routing protocols used across CNs reflects their adaptability (Saldana et al., 2016). For example, Guifi.net in Spain integrates Wi-Fi and fiber optics (Vega et al., 2012), whereas TakNet in Thailand relies on unlicensed 2.4 and 5 GHz bands, due to regulatory restrictions on sub-1 GHz frequencies like TV white space (APC, 2018).

This chapter intended to showcase the intertwined relationship between community networks and the theoretical framework of the commons. Far from being merely technical arrangements, CNs encompass social and political dimensions, inviting participatory governance, reshaping power dynamics in connectivity, and aiming to empower community members to actively participate in the internet.

Through the lens of the commons framework, it is possible to better understand how CNs operate: balancing issues of non-excludability and subtractability, negotiating collective ownership, and navigating the challenges of coordination, rule-making, and sustainability. Ostrom's principles for CPRs offer

valuable guidance for assessing CN governance. The case of guifi.net has been particularly well studied, especially from that perspective, illustrating the practical application of these ideas.

However, further research is needed to examine how less-explored cases in diverse contexts are adopting—or failing to adopt—these principles, and to assess the extent to which they function as laboratories for internet governance and as potential solutions to the digital divide. In particular, there is a notable lack of in-depth scholarship on digital sovereignty from a Global South perspective (Jiang & Belli, 2025).

Different and diverse local conditions, technical capacities, and social norms can significantly influence the management and development of CNs in other contexts and at different scales. With this theoretical foundation in place, the next chapters turn to the empirical dimension of this research, examining how these principles materialize in Colombian CN initiatives and what they reveal about the possibilities and limits of community-based digital infrastructure.

Chapter 3: Methodology

Because the perspectives of community network builders are central to this study, a qualitative methodology was adopted to capture participants' lived experiences and viewpoints. Context is crucial here, shaping both how these social phenomena occur and how they are interpreted.

Contrary to technological determinism, which assumes that technologies primarily drive social change (Chandler, 1996 as cited in Campbell & Russo, 2003), this research follows a social constructivist perspective, which holds that people shape technology (MacKenzie & Wajcman, 1985). The focus is on how communities build and govern infrastructure based on their own needs, rather than analyzing how they use it. Thus, the study uses a case study design focused on Colombia.

This research applies deductive reasoning, using theoretical concepts to assess the extent to which Colombian CNs align with the principles of the commons. At the same time, it remains open to emergent insights from the data, evaluating whether the commons framework adequately captures the complexities of CNs in this context.

3.1 Data collection methods

3.1.1. Interviews

To gather the data, semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted and document analysis was used. According to Creswell (2009), interviews enable researchers to encourage participants to explore areas they consider relevant to the research question. Semi-structured interviews involve a planned set of questions while allowing flexibility, combining both open- and closed-ended responses (Bowling & Ebrahim, 2005). Open-ended questions allow participants to express their perspectives freely, offering insights into the implementation of community networks, the management and governance of the infrastructure, the motivations behind and their insights about appropriation.

According to Robert Weiss in his book *Learning from Strangers* (1994), interviews allow us to access the observations of others, including places we have not visited or experiences we have not had, we can learn what people perceived and how

they interpreted their perceptions or the meanings to them of their relationships. Also, interviews are useful when the topic is complex, requires lengthy explanation, or when the topic or the questions may not be instantly clear to participants who may need some time to answer (Sheppard, 2020).

In this context, the decision to use individual interviews rather than other qualitative methods such as focus groups is motivated by the freedom and privacy they offer participants to express themselves without external pressure. Focus groups can be exposed to power imbalances among participants or risk that a single participant may dominate the discussion (D. L. Morgan & Hoffman, 2017).

From a critical point of view, during interviews the researcher has an active role generating data (H. Morgan, 2022). Researchers must remain aware that the way questions are framed can unintentionally guide participants' responses in ways that align with the researchers' own assumptions, potentially compromising the objectivity and integrity of the study (Roulston & Choi, 2017). In this case, the researcher is aware of that and tried to be transparent during the interactions with the interviewees and to be critical while conducting the interviews. Nevertheless, confirmation biases could arise.

This thesis analyzes seven community networks in Colombia, differing in geographical location, network size, and participant characteristics. Two of these networks were active more than a decade ago but are no longer functioning. Case selection was arbitrarily but purposely, guided by practical criteria, such as feasibility of contacting participants, geographic accessibility, willingness to collaborate, and type of technology used, rather than a systematic or random approach.

During recruitment, some limitations arose. Certain originally targeted networks could not be reached, making their inclusion unfeasible. For example, Jxa'h Wejxia was initially planned as part of the study but had to be excluded due to persistent communication challenges.

Given the researcher's external position, snowball sampling was used to recruit some of the interviewees, with initial contacts often facilitated by Colnodo, an NGO supporting community networks in Colombia. Coordinators of each network referred the researcher to additional participants, in addition, digital channels such as LinkedIn and email were also used to reach leaders and members of CN projects.

As a case study, some findings are context-specific and not easily generalizable to all Colombian or global community networks. In addition, to enhance validity and reduce bias, *data and methodological triangulation* were employed by using multiple sources and methods, and by seeking participants with varied roles and profiles. However, in most cases, only one participant per network was interviewed due to challenges such as internal dynamics, lack of trust in outsiders, or limited connectivity.

3.1.2. Document analysis

As mentioned before, in this research, data were gathered from various members of the community networks through interviews and supplemented with information from governance documents via document analysis. This dual approach allowed the researcher to examine the governance norms and frameworks established by these networks using different methods. In specific, four documents of sustainability and governance from community networks were analyzed.

With regard to document analysis, this research studies the documents where rules and guidelines in terms of governance and sustainability are written to identify and compare the specific practices and mechanisms developed by the members of each network. This analysis from the commons not only offered insights into the structural and contextual conditions shaping self-governance but also served as a complementary perspective to the interview data, enhancing the overall robustness of the research.

Document analysis involves a careful process of examining and interpreting data to understand meaning and generate empirical knowledge, just like other qualitative research methods (Bowen, 2009). Unlike data that results from direct interaction with research participants, documents are typically created independently of the researcher's influence. Here, the decisions and intervention of the researcher happens at the moment of interpretation and analysis of the content of the documents.

3.2 Sample: the chosen networks and organizations

The researcher acknowledges that seven CNs are not a representative sample, but rather a case study. By the moment of the empirical phase, at least fifteen CNs

were listed by the website redescomunitarias.co, managed by Colnodo. Five of those fifteen CNs were studied plus two inactive CNs. The community networks chosen for this research are listed below.

3.2.1. Red Almagrande

Red Almagrande, located on Colombia's Caribbean coast, began its design and implementation in 2023 and officially launched it in March 2024. Supported by Colnodo, the network currently operates with eight nodes, providing internet access to 32 families. It uses Starlink satellite technology combined with Wi-Fi at 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz frequencies. This initiative was developed as part of a project funded by the Google Impact Challenge for Women and Girls and implemented in partnership with the Corporación Colectiva de Comunicaciones Montes de María Línea 21 (CCMMaL21) (Colnodo, n.d.-c).

The network is located in Almagra, a small rural *corregimiento* (administrative division) in the municipality of Ovejas, in the department of Sucre. Corregimientos are rural subdivisions designed to improve service provision and ensure community participation in local public affairs (DANE, n.d.). Ovejas is part of the Montes de María region in the Colombian Caribbean, an area profoundly affected by armed conflict, particularly involving right-wing paramilitary groups and guerrilla forces. Between 1996 and 2003 alone, at least 42 massacres were recorded in the region. This violence was compounded by the massive dispossession and displacement of local communities, as well as social issues related to oil palm cultivation (Coljuristas, n.d.; Solidar Foundation, 2024). Despite this history of violence, Montes de María has strong traditions of resistance. In the mid-1990s, civil society and non-governmental organizations emerged as vital actors in confronting violence and fostering community resilience. Among them are Sembrando Paz and the Colectivo de Comunicaciones Línea 21 (Abitbol, 2022), the latter being a key ally in the creation of Red Almagrande.

3.2.2. La Cachuda

The process began in February 2024 and took place in camps with other two CNs (Jxa'h Wejxia Casil and Red INC,) promoted by Colnodo. This network has a license from the Colombian government to use the electromagnetic spectrum in the

900 MHz band. Additionally, the local internet provider, Nodo Pacífico, provides TV White Spaces technology.

The development of this network is part of the project "Connecting People: Implementing Community Networks with IMT Spectrum" within the Strengthening Communities /Improving Lives and Livelihoods (SCILLS). This initiative is led by Colnodo in alliance with the Inter-American Telecommunication Commission (CITEL) of the Organization of American States (OAS) and funded by ISOC. The network is located in the corregimientos of Juanchaco and Ladrilleros in Buenaventura on Colombia's Pacific coast. The only way to access these populated centers is by boat.

The total population of the corregimientos is approximately 2,200 people: 1,500 in Juanchaco and 700 in Ladrilleros (Colnodo, n.d.-d). The region faces various problems, including a lack of higher education infrastructure, illegal groups, solid waste management issues, natural disasters related to the sea, and the loss of cultural traditions due to modernization and tourism (Bernat, 2025; Colnodo, n.d.-d; Defensoría del Pueblo, 2017).

3.2.3. Red INC - Indígenas, Negros y Campesinos

Red INC is a project of community communication that started in the 2017, led by a very diverse group of communities from the *corregimientos* of El Porvenir and El Ceral in the municipality of Buenos Aires, Cauca, in the South West of Colombia. This project explores the use of different technologies for rural telephony services, local services and internet access (Colnodo, n.d.-e). It uses and experiments with Long-Term Evolution (LTE) technology in the 900 MHz band, TVWS, 2.4 and 5 GHz bands and mesh. Since the beginning, Red INC has been supported by Colnodo and various organizations and individuals who have joined the process, including ISOC, APC, Rhizomatica, Redes AC, and more. From 2024, Red INC is part of the project SCILLS.

Buenos Aires is a diverse, multicultural area in Cauca with a population of 32,000. Its inhabitants include Afro-Colombian communities, indigenous communities, peasant farmers, and former FARC guerrilla combatants (Colnodo, n.d.-e).

3.2.4. Red Poo'se Ajponũcarõ

Poo'se Ajponũcarõ translates to network-build in the Tukano language. In July 2023, it started in the Panuré and El Refugio Indigenous reservations, located in the municipality of San José del Guaviare in the southeastern Colombian Amazon (Colnodo, n.d.-b). The initiative was part of the Google Impact Challenge for Women and Girls project, "Connecting Opportunities for Women Entrepreneurs in Rural Areas of Colombia," and was made possible through the collaboration of ASOPAMURIMAJSA (the Association of Traditional Indigenous Authorities) and Colnodo. This CN currently uses Starlink satellital connexion as a provider.

In the Panuré reservation, the community is made up of 300 people and the Refugio reservation has around 230 people, both reservations are composed almost entirely of Tucano-Desano, Cubeo, Guanano, Piratapuyo, Sirianos, and other *pueblos* (Artesanías de Colombia, 2017).

3.2.5. Red A' Çxab Wejxa

The expression A' Çxab Wejxa means city of communication stars or connection in the indigenous language Nasa Yuwe. This community network is located in the rural *veredas* of Llanito and Cabuyo, belonging to the Piçkwe Ikh Resguardo, of the Nasa people, in the municipality of La Argentina, department of Huila, in the South-western part of Colombia. This CN started its process in March of 2024 and was launched in July of 2024, with the support of Colnodo and Plataforma Sur alliance, under the Google Impact Challenge project (Colnodo, n.d.-f). The network started with 8 points but now they have 19.

The network uses the technology of Libre router and the internet source uses Wi-Fi in the 2,4 GHz y 5GHz bands as well as satellite internet provided by Starlink. This network has an intranet with sections for culture, textiles, natural wealth and sharing their own seeds.

3.2.6. Bogota-Mesh

Bogota-Mesh was a wireless community network located in Bogotá, Colombia's capital city. It was built in 2010 and benefited around 800 people in the

localidad Ciudad Bolívar in the South of the city. The connectivity offered included intranet services such as communitarian chats, but also online services such as radio, email, education platforms, communitarian library and the protection to dangerous content (Rojas Rojas & Gordillo Ochoa, n.d.). The network was built with routers made in Colombia, and technology cloudmesh, using the free bands of the spectrum 2.4 and 5 GHz.

Bogota-Mesh was part of the initiative Redes Libre in Latin América. They, collectively build a manifesto that included: Ensures decentralization and prevents the monopolization of resources, coercion, or oppression; respects network neutrality; guarantees public and free access; its structure is that of a distributed network; growth is possible from any existing point; interconnection is carried out between peers who can publish or receive services and content under equal conditions; promotes the creation of other free networks, their interconnection, and interoperability. This manifesto was created at the 3rd Regional Conference of Redes Libres in Brazil, 2011 (Bogota-Mesh, 2012).

3.2.7. Bolivar Wireless

Bolivar Wireless was a wireless mesh network (WMN) developed in Bogota's *localidad* Ciudad Bolívar to provide affordable internet access and digital services to the communities. It was developed by the Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas (the public district university) in collaboration with local authorities and residents. The network used low-cost rooftop antennas connected in a mesh topology under the 2,4 GHz band.

In addition, Bolívar Wireless offered local services such as Wikipedia, e-learning platforms, chat, radio, blogs, and entertainment, hosted on local servers to minimize bandwidth needs and promote community engagement (Pedraza & Gómez, 2012). The reach of this network was very high, probably benefiting around one thousand people.

3.2.8 Organizations

In addition to interviewing community network participants, representatives from four key organizations were also interviewed: Colnodo, Fundación Karisma, the Association for Progressive Communications (APC), and the Internet Society (ISOC).

Colnodo, a Colombian NGO with over 30 years of experience, promotes the strategic use of ICTs for community development and leads efforts to advance community networks across the country (Colnodo, n.d.-a). **Fundación Karisma**, a civil society organization dedicated to defending human rights, freedom of expression, and gender and social equity in the digital sphere, has actively supported and promoted local networks in Colombia (Fundación Karisma, 2013).

The **Association for Progressive Communications (APC)**, since 1990, has worked to empower activists, grassroots organizations, and social movements, particularly in the Global South, to use ICTs strategically for democratic participation, gender equality, sustainable development, and digital rights. APC also plays a key role in enabling affordable internet access in underserved communities worldwide (APC, n.d.). **The Internet Society (ISOC)** works to expand internet access by supporting infrastructure deployment in underserved areas, building local technical skills, and promoting favorable policies on licensing, spectrum, and funding. It also partners with others to secure resources for local connectivity projects (ISOC, 2025).

For ease of reference, each interviewee has been assigned a unique code, which is used in the text to attribute quotes. Table 1 presents the list of participants along with their codes, roles, and the organizations or CNs they represent.

Code of participant	Organization / Community network	Role
I1	A' Çxab Wejxa	Coordinator of the core group
I2	Almagrande	Teacher / godfather of the network
I3	Almagrande	Coordinator of the core group
I4	Almagrande	Communicator / godmother of the network
I5	Almagrande	Member of the core group

I6	APC	Part of LocNet initiative from APC and Rhizomatica / Redes AC
I7	Bogota Mesh	Promoter of the network
I8	Bolivar Wireless	Teacher and promoter of the network
I9	Colnodo	Coordinator of the Community Networks
I10	Colnodo	Technical Coordinator Community Networks
I11	ISOC	Community Networks Project Lead and Communications and Outreach Manager for Latin America
I12	Karisma	Director
I13	La Cachuda	Coordinator of the core group
I14	La Cachuda	Member of the core group
I15	Poo'se Ajponũcarõ	Coordinator of the core group
I16	Red INC	Coordinator of the core group

Table 1. List of interviewees.

Code	Sustainability document from which network
D1	A' Çxab Wejxa
D2	Almagrande
D3	La Cachuda
D4	Poo'se Ajponũcarõ

Table 2. List of documents analyzed.

3.3 Data analysis

Content analysis of interviews and documents combined both inductive and deductive approaches. Categories were developed by the researcher, drawing on the theoretical frameworks as well as emerging themes from the interview data. The interviews were first transcribed using digital transcription software, followed by an initial review to identify preliminary categories. Based on this, the researcher created a codebook to guide the coding process. NVivo software was then used to

systematically categorize the data. To strengthen the validity of the findings, data from interviews and document analysis were triangulated and compared, resulting in a more comprehensive and robust analysis. The final set of categories and corresponding codes are presented below.

Governance methods

- Governance structures
- Meetings & Communication
- Decision-making
- Rule-making autonomy
- Monitoring & sanctions
- Conflict resolution
- Shared resources/responsibilities

Participants

- Role in the community
- Role in the CNs
- Inclusion/exclusion

Motivations

- Economic reasons
- Social reasons
- Educational reasons
- Connectivity reasons
- Personal growth
- Political resistance

Sustainability

- Economic models
- Infrastructure maintenance
- Transfer of knowledge/Building skills
- Social cohesion
- External support

Sovereignty

- Appropriation
- Contextual adaptation
- Independence from market
- Recognition before authorities

To check the whole thematic codebook with the explanation of the codes, please go to the Appendix section.

Chapter 4: Colombian community networks, an exercise of self-governance

The next two chapters bring together empirical findings and theoretical reflections to address the central research questions and contribute to academic discussions on community networks. Drawing from qualitative data collected in Colombian CNs, these sections link fieldwork insights to the theoretical framework centered on the concepts of commons, digital sovereignty, and self-determination.

The integration of findings, analysis, and discussion into a single narrative responds to the methodological choice to interpret empirical data through theoretical lenses. This structure enables a nuanced understanding of how community networks operate in practice, while highlighting their social and organizational dimensions.

This chapter, specifically, aims to answer the following research questions: What motivates communities to establish CNs in diverse Colombian contexts? (See section 4.1) Which governance methods are employed, and how do community members participate in decision-making, maintenance, and rule enforcement? (Sections 4.2 and 4.3) To what extent do these practices align with Ostrom's design principles for managing commons? (See section 4.3.)

By exploring these questions, the chapter emphasizes the role of CNs not only as technical solutions for connectivity, but also as collective projects rooted in local governance and autonomy. First, an overview about the motivations behind building CNs and a characterization of the profiles of the participants will take place. Then, it is presented a detailed analysis on the governance methods and structures, from the lenses of the commons.

4.1 Motivations of building CNs in Colombia

According to the literature and the theoretical framework, inverse or bottom-up infrastructure can be driven by motivations like reciprocity, self-interest and market-based dynamics (Egyedi & Vree, 2012). In the cases explored in this research, motivations vary from affordability and access to the internet, to social cohesion and education.

4.1.1. Connectivity

Following what Saldana et al. (2016) said, one of the motivations from participants of CNs is extending coverage to underserved areas and providing affordable internet access. In all cases studied in this research, the desire to build community networks is primarily motivated by the need for connectivity. Colombian networks are developed in areas without any internet connection or when it exists, it is very poor. I4 joked that not even “the sign of the cross” reached Almagra. Apart from the joke, it is evident that in those contexts fixed internet is absent and mobile internet coverage and quality are deficient.

D3 showed that the purpose of the CN project is to address “the lack of stable connectivity in the territory, where mobile telephone companies provide very limited coverage, and the few commercial internet operators that exist offer unstable services at high prices.” This statement underscores three key issues: internet reach, service quality, and affordability. Both interviewees and the sustainability documents emphasized these points, particularly focusing on the first layer of the digital divide, that is basic access to connectivity.

The urgency to connect the unconnected is reflected in calls from the UNDP, states projects, and local governments investments, that aim to bring internet connection to small towns and villages. I6 said, “nowadays, the whole issue of the accelerated race to connect the unconnected is not just about governments; it's also about companies and international organizations.” However, I6 said that sometimes these initiatives treat people in marginalized areas as mere consumers because they just install an access point and then leave.

For example, in the interviews it was mentioned the National Project of Optical Fiber. The Colombian government developed a project to bring optical fiber to 788 of the country's 1,234 municipalities in 27 of its 32 departments (MinTIC, 2024b). The project is expected to operate for 15 years and will provide infrastructure for telecommunications networks and service providers with a contractual agreement with Unión Temporal Fibra Óptica (Temporary Union of Optical Fiber). The ICT Ministry (MinTIC) is also developing the National High-Speed Connectivity Project, which plans to deploy high-speed connectivity infrastructure in 29 municipalities and 18 non-municipalized areas of the country, located in 11 departments. The

project aims to use wireless solutions (microwave and satellite) and/or other viable technical, economic, and logistical alternatives (MinTIC, 2024a).

However, as mentioned by I9 and I10, these projects have a limited reach. For example, the optical fiber usually only has coverage in the urban areas of the municipalities, or in the cases where it is brought to rural areas it tends to be very isolated, located in public schools or medical attention points. In addition, in some cases, the prices to access the service are too high due to maintenance fees and low rentability.

In addition, geographical conditions make it difficult to provide internet to these regions. The majority of the CNs analyzed are located not just in rural areas but in very difficult places with ecosystems of jungle, mountains, and more. I13, from the Pacific coast, mentioned “the only means of transportation to get here is by boat. We don't have roads and there is too much jungle. That is why here the issue of the digital divide is quite complex”.

Furthermore, due to those geographical conditions and characteristics of the analyzed places, providing technical support when the network is not working can be very difficult. This issue was constantly mentioned, highlighting the difficulty of fixing damaged equipment or restoring services. I2, a teacher from a rural school in Los Montes de María and godfather of the Almagrande network, said:

“When it is necessary to do maintenance [to the internet infrastructure], we have to pray to all the saints and ask God to help that technician. The school rector has to call them, then the technicians try to get there [if the road and climate conditions allow them] and then they show up and do the signal recovery exercise. It is a whole odyssey. Why? Because the road is not good, because there are armed groups, because the administrative processes are negligent, ect...”

In this context, rurality is often equated with non-connectivity. However, the lack of internet access is not exclusively a rural issue. Even some urban areas, including neighborhoods within major cities, remain unconnected due to factors such as geographical barriers, lack of competition among providers, state neglect, and other structural challenges. As mentioned by Ostrom (1990), the physical and symbolic distance from administrative centers not only affects access to services but

can also shape the degree of community autonomy. This dynamic is evident in the two urban CNs analyzed in this research, both were located in Bogotá, in neighbourhoods where residents experienced limited connectivity and, in some aspects, state abandonment. In these cases, the need for basic services emerged as a key driver for building and sustaining community-managed infrastructure.

“It is because something we have learned is that when there is no real human need, there is not so much acceptance and there is not so much collaboration. If I came to the north [in more comfortable neighborhoods] and set up an antenna where 80% of the citizens already have access to internet, they do not see the added value. They say 'why am I going to connect a network and why am I going to buy a repeater antenna? If I already have it here and I can access the internet'. But if I go to the south, where less than 50% or 30% of the population had internet access at that time, they saw it as a necessity,” I7 clarified.

Once connectivity problems are solved, initiatives like CNs may be seen as unnecessary. For example, BolivarWireless and Bogota-Mesh stopped providing service for various reasons, one of which was that there was no longer a need for connectivity. In that context CNs became irrelevant when private or public providers started offering connections. As I8 mentioned, it became easier to access the internet with more commercial options available, so many people preferred to just pay for access.

4.1.2. Economic reasons / affordability

Beyond connectivity itself, including service quality and availability, economic factors emerged as a common motivation among interviewees. Several participants emphasized that, in areas where private ISPs provide mobile services, the quality is often poor while prices remain high. Costs vary depending on the provider, the specific services offered, and, in some cases, zero-rating practices.

In 2021, the Colombian NGO El Veinte challenged a provision of Law 1450 of 2011 that allowed mobile internet providers to design offers based on user profiles, which resulted in zero-rating plans in which certain apps chosen by the ISPs were exempted from data consumption. The organization argued that such practices, rather than democratizing internet access, create a divided internet: one for

vulnerable and low-income communities and another for those who can afford unrestricted access (El Veinte, 2025). More than three years after, Colombia's Constitutional Court ruled on the issue, declaring unconstitutional the challenged provision and granting a one-year period for the ruling's implementation (Corte Constitucional de Colombia, n.d.).

Following this, in terms of the mobile internet plans offered to the communities analyzed, some participants noted that private providers may charge between 30,000 and 60,000 Colombian pesos (approximately 8 to 15 euros) and that prices continuously increase. One interviewee, I16, shared that prices were too high and quality too bad:

“A few years ago, when our network had to stop working, two providers came to sell the internet, but it was very expensive. People couldn't afford it because two megabytes costed 40,000 pesos. The next year, those same two megabytes costed 50,000. And now, this year, they cost 60,000. And when you try to look something up in the dictionary, just a single word, the loading circle starts spinning because it won't load.”

In contrast, the average monthly fee for internet access in the community networks studied is around 20,000 COP (5 euros). This amount is determined by the community and based on the operational costs of the network. According to the literature, as non-profit systems, CNs reinvest collected funds into maintenance of infrastructure, salaries, utility costs, and the rental of spaces where antennas are located. According to interviewees, people do not receive salaries but funds mostly go toward paying backbone providers such as Starlink or local ISPs, and saving for unforeseen expenses such as maintenance or purchasing of equipment.

Economic motivations are not limited to high prices charged by private providers, but also include the desire to stimulate the local economy. In all the sustainability documents and several interviews, improving the exchange of goods was identified as a key expectation. I15, for example, highlighted that, in their context, women entrepreneurs are often disconnected from digital technologies. However, after gaining internet access, and more importantly, while participating in digital communication workshops, they felt empowered and began to promote and sell their handicrafts, products and services online.

This trend is evident in agricultural and tourism-focused communities, where members of CNs have used the internet to advertise services, exchange goods, and access education. As I13 explained: “Beyond just providing a connection, it was also an opportunity for women to showcase their businesses. Since we are in a tourist area, many women are taking the opportunity to show their talents, their knowledge, and our ancestral heritage.”

4.1.3. Educational reasons

Educational motivations also emerged as a recurring theme in the interviews. Almost all participants from CNs mentioned the importance of internet access for both children and adults who wish to study. This need includes two key dimensions: access to information for school assignments and access to educational resources such as online courses and training programs. Additionally, in the projects supported by Colnodo, communities receive computers that are made available for collective use, for example, to help children complete their homework.

I15 noted: “The idea was that our young people and we adults as well would have the opportunity to study remotely, especially now that we have access to virtual courses.” Following the same idea, I9 said: “How to act or contribute so that people don't have to leave their territory, so they're not always looking for opportunities elsewhere. But instead, through this activity, they can continue studying.”

Additionally, interviewees emphasized the value of the technical training that accompanies the design and implementation of community networks. Community members are not only learning how to use the internet but also gaining an understanding of how it works and how they can expand it. This learning process is particularly significant for members of the core managing groups and those who take on technical support roles.

4.1.4. Social cohesion and community empowerment

Existing literature emphasizes that community empowerment and social cohesion are central motivations behind CN initiatives. While the empirical findings of this research also reflect these elements, they appear less prominently than economic and connectivity-related reasons. Nevertheless, social cohesion and

collaborative strategies appear to be fundamental to start the projects and in the long-term sustainability of community networks.

I6 noted that one of the primary goals of CNs is to strengthen rural, Indigenous, and farmer communities by enabling them to create their own systems of communication and connectivity. He emphasized that “as the collective and the people within the network continue to grow, they begin to understand more, and they start to realize that it is their right to have these communication processes, especially in marginalized communities.”

Similarly, I13 highlighted the communal nature of the CN, explaining her personal commitment because she has seen the benefits of the community: “That has been our main motivation, to dedicate time, to stay up late, to set aside the things we have to do, to give up potential income, all so we can dedicate more time to the community network.” All of these can happen because, according to the theory, in common resources, the shared context, cultural and institutional background motivates cooperation.

Besides, as discussed in the literature review, CNs have the potential to empower individuals to become active digital citizens and to exercise their civic rights. This potential is reflected in local practices through growing awareness across political, environmental, and cultural dimensions. I4 described this vision:

“More than just bringing the internet or getting people in front of screens, what really matters to us is continuing to foster training for people to become political subjects with rights, conscious individuals who understand that defending the environment, the land, and cultivating new seeds are also rights. That the *campesino* [rural/farmer] way of life and thinking and their long struggles, may one day lead to a more dignified life.”

Even so, it is difficult to establish a clear causal relationship between community networks and the emergence of civic empowerment. Yet, the empirical findings suggest that a certain degree of pre-existing community empowerment is often a prerequisite for initiating the process of building such infrastructure. In other words, CNs tend to emerge from contexts where communities are already organized and capable of collective action, rather than creating these conditions from scratch.

In addition to all mentioned, other motivations surfaced during fieldwork, those include personal growth and technical curiosity. For example, I1 spoke about how interesting it is for her to learn how to deal with cables and internet infrastructure, while I7 highlighted the enthusiasm of young people for experimenting with technology, sharing knowledge, and engaging with the free software movement.

Additionally, the theoretical framework situates the commons as contributing to the common good, countering passive citizenship, and strengthening civil society and democracy (Hess & Ostrom, 2007). In some cases, Colombian CNs were also framed as expressions of political resistance. This perspective was echoed by I4, who reflected: “Four or five years later [of the beginning of the CN], there is now a restored social fabric. As you could hear from them, they are autonomous, and they have their own voice, both public and political.” Similarly, I6 observed: “We are now moving beyond seeing these communities as mere recipients of public policy, and instead recognizing them as actors, agents of change and transformation, who can generate and take ownership of this connectivity.”

As commons-based resources, community networks also strive for sustainability to ensure they continue serving their communities. Interviewees emphasized the importance of keeping the networks operational and delivering tangible benefits, with sustainability becoming a motivation in itself. As I13 explained, their dream is not to improve network’s speed or quality, but rather to reach those who are most in need: “We want others to also benefit from our connectivity, as we meet these needs as Black communities.” This resonates with the theoretical framework of the commons that says that in CPRs appropriators share a common interest in maintaining and preserving the resource for long-term use.

Taken together, these testimonies and reflections suggest that, as highlighted in the academic literature, the objectives of community networks extend far beyond providing mere internet access. Nonetheless, basic connectivity remains the most frequently cited motivation in the fieldwork. As mentioned by Saldana et al. (2016), the reasons for building CNs vary across communities, contexts, and individuals. But when seen as common resources, these networks transcend access provision to become drivers of economic development, educational opportunities, and social

cohesion. At the same time, following the commons framework, they are designed with an emphasis on sustainability, ensuring their continued ability to serve the needs of the community.

4.2 Participants/stakeholders

From a commons-based perspective, the collective governance of Colombian community networks reveals a range of meaningful dynamics and characteristics. Analyzing them requires examining the interplay between people, technology (as a resource), and territory. Focusing first on the human dimension, specifically the roles individuals play and how they interact with the network, offers valuable insight into the relationships that sustain and shape these initiatives.

The relationship between people and infrastructure is shaped by their roles and levels of involvement. In the cases studied, a variety of stakeholders participate in the design, deployment, use, and maintenance of the networks. Five levels of interaction were identified:

1. International, regional and local organizations, which primarily support CN development and engage in advocacy;
2. National and local governments, including public authorities and policymakers responsible for regulating spectrum use and addressing the digital divide;
3. Local organizations that manage the networks (present in some but not all cases); and/or a core or management team, often referred to as the *grupo gestor* in networks promoted by Colnodo;
4. The broader community, which is located in the territory and uses and benefits from the network;
5. Universities and academic institutions, involved in researching or supporting the development of CNs (present in a few cases).

4.2.1. International, regional and national organizations

Within the first group, *international or regional organizations*, the Internet Society (ISOC) and the Association for Progressive Communications (APC) are widely recognized for their investment in and advocacy for community networks.

Additionally, organizations such as Rhizomatica, Altermundi, and Redes A.C. have played significant roles in supporting rural and Indigenous communities across Latin America in building autonomous communication infrastructures.

Several of the community networks analyzed in this study maintain relationships with these international actors. For example, La Cachuda and Red INC were both established through the SCILLS program (Strengthening Communities/Improving Lives and Livelihoods), funded by the Internet Society Foundation. This initiative was implemented through a collaboration between Colnodo, the Inter-American Telecommunication Commission (CITEL) of the Organization of American States (OAS), and the Internet Society Foundation. In the case of Poo'se Ajponũcarõ, its development is part of the project Connecting Opportunities for Women Entrepreneurs in Rural Areas of Colombia, managed by Colnodo and funded by the Google.org Impact Challenge for Women and Girls (Impact Challenge with Google, n.d.).

In the interviews with APC and ISOC, they emphasized that both organizations engage in advocacy related to digital governance and internet infrastructure. ISOC, in particular, aims to create an enabling environment for the development of internet access infrastructure by addressing regulatory, capacity-related, and sustainability barriers. The Internet Society Foundation also offers grants for network deployment, as mentioned earlier.

At the national level, Colnodo stands out as the most influential organization supporting CNs in Colombia. Of the seven networks studied in this research, five were developed with Colnodo's support. The organization provides technical, social, and communications training; engages in advocacy to raise the visibility and legitimacy of CNs as a viable alternative for bridging the digital divide; and acts as a key intermediary between civil society, academia, public authorities, and the private sector.

As I9 explained, advocacy efforts also aim to secure public funding, not just recognition: "In the case of Colnodo, up to now, all the networks we have supported have been funded through international cooperation resources. So far, there has not been any funding from the state that enables these networks to be developed."

As seen in the literature review, partnerships are vital for the creation and maintenance of the CNs. However, they can also bring risks of autonomy and independence. It is valid to ask if the communities would be able to start and maintain the network without external support. Efforts are made to boost the communities to be autonomous and sustainable, nevertheless, technical support is still needed after years. In addition, as Gwaka et al. (2023) noted, the presence of single dominant partners could determine the priorities of the projects. That is evident in the project from Google Impact Challenge, that puts in the center the development and growth of women and girls.

4.2.2. National and local authorities

The second group, *national and local authorities*, emerged in the cases studied from two main perspectives: as regulatory agents, particularly regarding radio spectrum use, and as potential enablers of innovation. At a minimum, it is expected that these institutions refrain from creating unnecessary obstacles to network development and autonomy, as emphasized by I12. This aligns with Ostrom's seventh design principle, which states that "the rights of appropriators to devise their own institutions are not challenged by external governmental authorities," (Ostrom, 1990, p. 101). That means that government actors should at least recognize that they are not the sole authorities over rule-making and allow communities the autonomy to govern their own networks.

Regarding the first perspective, in Colombia, the use of the radio spectrum is regulated by the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications (MinTIC), which is responsible for defining public policy; and the National Spectrum Agency (ANE - Agencia Nacional del Espectro), which oversees spectrum planning, monitoring, and control. The ANE operates under the direction of MinTIC.

Historically, spectrum allocation in Colombia has followed a centralized model, with auctions held every four to five years. These processes often take more than a year to conclude (ANE, 2025). For instance, in 2023, the MinTIC spectrum auction allocated four nationwide blocks of 80 MHz in the 3.5 GHz band, generating approximately COP 1.37 trillones in revenue (equivalent to about USD 1.37 billion) (MinTIC, n.d.). MinTIC reported that through the *Obligaciones de Hacer* attached to spectrum licenses, operators are mandated to invest approximately COP 389.7 billion

(about USD 100 million) to deploy fiber-optic internet in 1,191 educational institutions, benefiting some 73,093 students over a 20-year period. These initiatives are presented as part of broader efforts to close the digital divide (MinTIC, n.d.).

In the Colombian context, community networks operate under highly diverse conditions and often rely on alternative approaches to access spectrum. Most CNs, as noted in the literature, build their infrastructure using unlicensed spectrum—a strategy observed in initiatives like Bogota-Mesh and BolivarWireless, which operated in the 2.4 and 5 GHz band and expanded coverage through mesh nodes. This reliance on unlicensed bands stems from the fact that licensed spectrum is typically reserved for entities with exclusive rights, such as commercial operators or government agencies (Belli et al., 2016; Gwaka et al., 2023).

Yet not all CNs can rely solely on unlicensed bands. In many regions, especially remote or rugged areas, networks must integrate various technologies such as International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT), satellite links, or TV White Spaces (TVWS). As I10 explained, technology choices depend on the availability of local infrastructure, for example, whether there is a nearby fiber-optic line that can be extended, or whether satellite connectivity is the only feasible option for establishing backhaul. “That is to solve the backhaul issue when neither radiolink nor fiber is possible. In that case, Starlink was the quickest option, it's a nearly disruptive technology compared to what existed before. It's not really comparable to other satellite operators,” I10 said.

Contrary to the unlicensed bands, the use of licensed spectrum comes under formal regulation. For example, Red INC holds a license to use a specific portion of the spectrum in the 900 MHz. Meanwhile, organizations such as Dynamic Spectrum Alliance and Colnodo have actively advocated for policy reforms to allocate additional spectrum bands to community-led initiatives. In Colombia, Colnodo is currently campaigning for a portion of the 900 MHz IMT band to be made available for community networks. I10 explained that the government has not yet initiated the auction or allocation process for this band: “The core of the argument is: 'Let's change the regulation and allow a slice of this band to be used for this purpose, so communities can deploy their own networks.'”

4.2.3. Local organizations and core groups

The third group consists of highly local organizations or core management teams responsible for overseeing the network. These entities may be pre-existing community organizations or newly formed groups created specifically to manage the community networks. In the cases promoted by Colnodo, a *grupo gestor* is selected by the community on a voluntary basis. This group receives most of the technical training related to the installation of routers, antennas, and cables; as well as the sustainability and governance recommendations. Generally, they do not receive financial compensation for their work, although in some cases they benefit from a reduction in the fee for access.

This way, when conceived as commons, community networks often establish nested groups to manage and govern their operations. Both the literature and the empirical findings of this research highlight that cohesive and committed management groups are a key condition for sustaining these networks over time. In fact, some community network initiatives do not even begin unless there are already established organizations capable of taking on this oversight role. As I6 emphasized:

“Many times, these organizations are ones that have been around for several years. They started with basic services, then moved on to productive processes, then savings cooperatives, and now they are deeply involved in telecommunications. So, the people in leadership roles are often adults, and sometimes even older adults, but the ones who are showing the most interest in telecommunications are also the youth.”

In other cases, such as Bogota-Mesh and BolivarWireless, no formal managing group existed. Instead, the networks were built and maintained by volunteers who made decisions collectively with the community, but without forming a dedicated core group. Both I7 and I8 developed the mesh network with friends, fellow students and teachers, and other tech enthusiasts. However, they had the support and work in alliance of local community and neighborhood organizations.

In some cases the organizations are *juntas de acción communal*, which are the largest community leadership organized civil structure in Colombia, conformed by social and political leaders from the communities. According to the official data, there are at least 45.000 *juntas* in the whole country. The Ministry of Interior has

highlighted their importance in the development of infrastructure such as bridges, roads, health points of attention, police stations posts, marketplaces, and self-built housing programs (MinInterior, n.d.). In the case of BolivarWireless that was fundamental to develop the network: “We had support from the *junta de acción comunal*, the leaders also took ownership of the project, so to speak. They helped us set up, for example, the servers in the community hall and in different houses around the neighborhood,” I8 said.

Another key communal structure in the analyzed community networks is the *Consejos Comunitarios* (Community Councils), which serve as the ethnic authority responsible for managing the Collective Territories of Black, Afro-Colombian, Raizal, and Palenquera communities. As described by Unidad de Restitución de Tierras et al. (2016), “Community Councils are made up of all the people who are part of the community or communities that have ancestrally inhabited the territory and share cultural traditions, history, and a collective sense of identity.” An example is the network La Cachuda, which has a *grupo gestor* whose work is intertwined with two *consejos comunitarios* from the *corregimientos* of Juanchaco and Ladrilleros.

In other cases, the organizations managing the network are Indigenous authorities, such as those in the Indigenous council or other Indigenous governance structures. For instance, the initial engagement with the reserves for the network Poo’sé Ajponũcarõ was made through the National Organization of the Indigenous Peoples of the Colombian Amazon (OPIAC), with final community support provided by ASOPAMURIMAJSA (Association of Traditional Indigenous Authorities). For the network A’ Çxab Wejxa, the managing group is made up of Nasa Indigenous people from the Piçkwe Ikh reserve.

Within managing groups and supporting organizations, smaller subgroups are sometimes formed to focus on specific areas such as technical operations, communications, or administration. This can be interpreted as the nested enterprises mentioned by Ostrom as the eighth design principle.

In practice, however, these subgroups often dissolve over time, or their membership significantly decreases. This trend was consistent across the CNs studied. During the initial planning and design phases, *grupos gestores* often consisted of 12 to 14 members, but over time this number may shrink to just four,

two or even one person managing the network. This reduction presents clear challenges for long-term sustainability and questions democratic governance structures.

Moreover, when assessing participation, two key dimensions emerge: the extent to which the network reflects the community's diversity and the risks of power imbalances when decision-making becomes concentrated within a small group. In terms of diversity, CNs try to include diverse profiles and demographics of the community. One of the CNs studied assigned one representative per *vereda* (a rural settlement within a larger administrative area), even when the network does not reach all the *veredas*.

In terms of gender, Gwaka et al. (2023) emphasize that women within community networks play a pivotal role in reducing the gender digital divide and fostering meaningful access to connectivity. Across all the active CNs studied, women simultaneously hold prominent leadership positions within their families and broader community structures. Notably, several initiatives supporting these networks intentionally place women at the center of their design and implementation, contributing to more inclusive and equitable outcomes. Furthermore, women actively engage as users, leveraging technology to promote their businesses and enhance their livelihoods.

That said, the potential for exclusion still exists in subtle and context-specific ways. As Bidwell (2019) notes, some social and decision-making spaces and learning processes, contrary to common assumptions, can inadvertently contribute to exclusion. In the cases studied, certain practices may unintentionally exclude participants; for example, when meetings are scheduled at the same time as other community events or during periods when farmers are busy with agricultural work.

While it was difficult to clearly identify such instances in the interviews, possible disparities may relate to age, geographic remoteness, or diversity. For instance, individuals living farther from access nodes or outside densely populated areas often face greater challenges in actively participating in network governance. This geographic barrier is also a common reason why members of the *grupo gestor* are sometimes forced to withdraw, as attending meetings or reaching key network points can become logistically unfeasible.

As mentioned in the theory, one of the big critiques to Ostrom's commons framework is overlooking power relationships and imbalances. In the case of the networks analyzed, a decline in active participation can lead to a significant reduction in representativeness and unbalances of power. For example, if a core group initially composed of 12 members—intended to broadly represent the community—shrinks to only four active participants after several months, its ability to reflect diverse community interests is severely compromised. This reduction not only undermines representational legitimacy but also concentrates decision-making authority and technical responsibilities in the hands of a few individuals.

Despite these challenges, the CNs generally make efforts to be inclusive, reflecting a broad spectrum of demographic and cultural characteristics. A particularly illustrative case is RedINC, where the network explicitly embraces and embodies the community's diversity—not only in its name (Red de Indígenas, Negros y Campesinos) but also in its membership and leadership.

4.2.4. The community / users

The fourth group identified is the *broader community*, the people who use the internet provided by the CN. As in the commons framework, the community shares territory, resources, and rules. In the Colombian context, most of the CNs analyzed are located in remote rural areas, far from urban centers and the public infrastructure they offer. Geographically, these areas are often challenging and difficult to access, located in jungles, mountains, and farmland. The residents are typically small-scale farmers, artisans, tourism workers, and others engaged in local, territory-related activities.

According to Ostrom's theory, appropriators are individuals who withdraw resource units from a common-pool resource system. They are directly affected by the operational rules and, in well-functioning commons, should be able to participate in modifying these rules (Ostrom, 1990). Similarly, the literature on community networks highlights that the community is an active participant in the network. Their level of engagement in rule-making processes and infrastructure maintenance varies depending on social dynamics and local context.

In the cases studied, the community members primarily act as users: they benefit from the network but also contribute to its sustainability, mainly by paying fees. CNs are generally organized as non-profit initiatives, meaning that any collected funds are reinvested in the maintenance and development of the network. Findings from this study confirm that this is the case for the Colombian CNs analyzed. These networks have developed economic models to calculate the minimum income required to sustain operations and, in some instances, have even managed to build savings to fund repairs or network expansion.

An important aspect to highlight is Colnodo's role during the initial design and deployment phases. Colnodo allocates resources to purchase the necessary infrastructure, such as antennas, cables, routers, computers, which are then legally transferred to the local organization. Additionally, Colnodo covers the initial months of internet service where needed. For instance, as of now, the monthly fee for Starlink is around 250,000 COP (approximately €55). Some networks began collecting fees from users from the moment service became available, allowing them to build financial reserves for future maintenance.

Depending on the model, some members of the community pay a fixed monthly fee, while others opt for daily or weekly payments. Monthly fees typically range between 15,000 and 25,000 COP (€3 to €5), while daily usage costs between 1,000 and 3,000 COP (€0.20 to €0.60). According to interviewees, these prices are significantly lower than those of commercial mobile services, and much more affordable than the few fixed internet options available in those areas. In certain cases, there are additional charges for using the computers.

One of the most interesting findings is the sense of solidarity within these communities. When a member cannot afford to pay on time, others understand and support them. As I2 explained: "We have to understand that there are people who don't even earn a basic salary, who are making a living day by day. We have to be very reasonable, respectful, and calm. Because otherwise the network could fall apart." Besides, I16 said that she only need the people to inform her that they cannot pay on time and they agree on a payment as soon as possible, but without cutting the service: "we have given them all the facilities, because this is community, this is not mine, it is for all of us to benefit from the internet."

Beyond user fees, members of the managing group and the broader community organize fundraising activities to support the network. From selling baked goods to hosting soccer tournaments, they have devised creative ways to cover operating expenses. In some cases, the community chooses not to charge certain users, for example, rural schools that have been equipped with routers and internet service.

However, in some networks, the broader community participates primarily as users who exchange money for the service provided. Beyond the *grupo gestor* and a few volunteers involved in technical or administrative maintenance, most community members engage with the network only as end-users. They generally do not possess the technical knowledge required to address problems when they arise and instead rely on the *grupo gestor* to resolve issues.

4.2.5. Universities and academia

The fifth group identified is *universities* and *academia*. This group was mentioned in only a few interviews, typically in reference to students or professors interested in researching or forming partnerships with community networks. In some instances, communities sought these collaborations to gain visibility or improve access to educational services. In the two cases based in Bogotá, academic actors, including students, research groups, and professors, were actually the driving force behind the creation and development of the networks. However, in the broader Colombian context, the relationship between academia and CNs still appears to be limited.

In sum, Colombian community networks emerge from a rich and diverse ecosystem of actors and stakeholders, each contributing in distinct yet interconnected ways to the design, implementation, and sustainability of these initiatives. From international advocates and national intermediaries to local managing teams, community members, and academic allies, the human dimension of CNs underscores the complexity of building and maintaining digital and infrastructural commons in rural and underserved contexts.

Yet, challenges remain, particularly around representation, institutional support, and long-term capacity. Internal dynamics shape the degree of participation

of each group and influence how these actors interact with one another. Authorities, for instance, engage with the networks in ways that differ significantly from end-users or core managing teams. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for analyzing how governance is structured within CNs, a topic explored in the following section.

4.3 Governance mechanisms

As discussed in the theoretical chapters, the commons are fundamentally about governance, understood as the collectively defined rules and commitments that regulate access to and sustain shared resources. In the context of community networks, governance encompasses the agreements and practices established by the appropriators themselves. This section examines these mechanisms based on empirical findings, through the lens of commons framework.

As mentioned before, Elinor Ostrom identified eight design principles for the sustainable management of common-pool resources after analyzing numerous commons-based projects. This section examines the extent to which these principles are present in the governance and practices of the Colombian CNs studied.

The following table summarizes their application. A ✓ indicates that, according to interviews and sustainability documents, the principle is clearly present in the CN. A ~ suggests that the principle may be partially present, context-dependent, or not explicitly documented. An × indicates that the principle is not applied in any form within the CN.

The list of principles is:

1. Clear defined boundaries
2. Correlation between rules and local conditions
3. Collective choice arrangements
4. Effective monitoring
5. Graduated sanctions mechanisms
6. Conflict resolution mechanisms
7. Right to be recognized by authorities
8. Nested enterprises

Principle / CN	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
Almagrande	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
La Cachuda	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	~	✓	✓
Red INC	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	~	✓	~
Poo'se Ajponũcarõ	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	~	✓	~
A' Çxab Wejxa	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	~	✓	✓
BogotaMesh	~	✓	~	✓	~	~	✓	~
BolivarWireless	~	✓	~	✓	~	~	✓	~

Table 3. Governance principles in Colombian CNs.

While the table provides a synthesized overview of the principles, a deeper analysis is essential to capture the complexity of community networks and their governance. The following section offers a detailed examination of the governance mechanisms and the application of Ostrom's design principles. Because these principles are often interrelated in practice, the analysis is presented in a more fluid and integrated manner rather than as a rigid, principle-by-principle discussion.

Ostrom, as the first principle, said that boundaries need to be clear and that could make outsiders excluded. In the case of the studied CNs, in some cases the network remains open, without any filter or code to access. However, most of them now have captive portals and identification access points to close it to outsiders. Ostrom (1990) explains that without closing CPRs, the individuals that invested in it might have less return as they expected, but that also in extreme cases, it could lead to overuse or destruction of the resource. Here the free-riding or congestion problems could arise.

To counter that, when new participants join the network, they agree to a range of conditions: hosting equipment in their homes (with the associated increase in energy use), learning to manage connectivity devices, and complying with payment agreements. D3, for instance, states: "If new members are going to join, they must

receive training, fulfill commitments and agreements, understand the internal regulations, and sign a commitment document.”

But even with individual and not public access to the network, some cases of congestion can happen. In one of the networks, some of the appropriators have been complaining because other appropriators use the network to play videogames, which takes a lot of the speed of the network. Here, one could bring Hardin’s tragedy of the commons (1968). However, since the people playing videogames are also contributing with their fees, it could be difficult to exclude them and against the idea of having a free internet. In terms of congestion, some networks implement usage regulations such as identification to access and limits on the number of devices allowed per household.

According to Ostrom (1990), one of the reasons that appropriation of CPRs maintain autonomy in modifying their own rules is their physical and institutional distance from local authorities and administrators. This relative isolation can foster self-governance and encourage localized rule-making. Within community network initiatives, there is a similarly clear aspiration to establish collective and democratic models for managing technological resources. I6 stressed their commitment to horizontal, participatory structures, while also recognizing the variation in how such governance models are put into practice across different communities.

“We don’t make the decisions, the communities do. How they choose to organize internally is up to them. Some networks have assemblies where members come together, hold meetings, and make decisions. Others are more embedded in the community’s existing structures. In some cases, they designate three or four people to oversee the network. There are also networks strongly supported by *cabildos* (Indigenous councils), by organizations, or by a *grupo gestor*,” he explained.

Among the networks still in operation, the presence of a *grupo gestor* is a recurring feature. In most cases, decisions, such as those related to fees or locations for new nodes and mostly all the technical work is done by this team. This dynamic reflects what Ostrom (1990) refers to as collective-choice arrangements, where most appropriators can participate in modifying the norms. However, as previously mentioned, the number of active participants in these groups tends to decrease over

time. This suggests challenges in sustaining broad engagement, a common issue in long-term commons management.

In terms of decision-making and governance structures, local organizations, such as Indigenous authorities, *consejos comunitarios*, or *juntas de acción comunal*, play varying roles depending on their internal governance structures and the scope of decisions being made. As I1 noted: “We work with the *grupo gestor*, and mostly we manage things here in the *vereda*, with the whole community. From time to time, the authority from the [Indigenous] reserve, the governor, supports us on that front.” This arrangement echoes Ostrom’s principle of nested enterprises, where governance occurs at multiple levels, from the community to the broader territorial authorities.

A similar arrangement is found in the La Cachuda network, where their sustainability document outlines: “The core organizational structure was defined as the *grupo gestor*, which is divided into technical, administrative, and communications teams. Decisions will be validated by the community councils of Juanchaco and Ladrilleros, as well as by the community assembly.” This layered decision-making process exemplifies how polycentric governance can emerge, with different authorities sharing responsibilities for oversight and validation. Different levels are mentioned, the *grupo gestor*, two community councils, and the assembly, extended to the whole community. This reflects the recognition of rights to organize, ensuring that local authorities are not bypassed but instead integrated into network governance, a design principle that Ostrom identifies. For instance, I13 further clarified regarding the *consejo comunitario*:

“The process always went hand in hand with the Community Council, which manages and oversees territorial matters. As a community network, we don’t act or do anything without their prior approval. They are informed of all actions and help replicate the benefits the network brings.”

In cases where individuals hold dual roles, such as being both community leaders and Indigenous governors or mayors, these responsibilities can intertwine. However, none of the interviewees reported any resulting tensions or conflicts. This suggests a degree of institutional compatibility, where overlapping roles reinforce rather than undermine the network’s governance processes.

From a different perspective, Bogota-Mesh operated in a more informal way, lacking a clearly defined governance structure. Instead, it relied on a participatory model with three layers, and nested enterprises as Ostrom identified: a core team that set protocols and oversaw deployments; a broader group of technically-inclined collaborators who followed and replicated the model; and the wider community, which interacted with the network as learners and users but did not make any decision in terms of technical or governance structures. While not involved in formal decision-making, they accepted responsibilities linked to their participation. I7 reflected: “In free software communities, you want things to be horizontal, and I always encouraged everyone to make decisions together. But there are always people who, to some extent, end up having to decide on their own.”

In a different aspect, communication tools and practices differ across CNs, shaped by local conditions. Assemblies and meetings are usually coordinated through instant messaging platforms like WhatsApp, phone or online calls, and word-of-mouth. The frequency of meetings varies depending on the urgency and type of issue. In addition, WhatsApp groups are used not only by core teams but also sometimes by the wider community. Initially created for technical coordination, these groups often evolve into general community channels used to announce training opportunities or even report local concerns, such as a missing pet.

In other aspects, regardless of the governance structure in place, recurring topics in meetings include technical performance and financial sustainability. I3 explained how decisions are typically made: “We meet as a grupo gestor and make decisions collectively. If a family wants to join and there’s a router nearby, we discuss it, and if everyone agrees, we install the access point.”

Each CN defines its own participation and decision-making mechanisms. D2, for example, states: “During management group meetings, those who do not attend do not have decision-making power. [...] Decisions are made by a simple majority: half plus one of attendees.” This quorum-based decision-making approach was consistently found across the documents analyzed. Yet, some networks aim for full consensus, as illustrated by I16:

“We have a savings fund and currently need some batteries. But we haven’t been able to gather all the coordinators, so I can’t just say, ‘Let’s buy them.’ I

worry that if only five of us agree and the others don't, they might say I should cover the cost myself.”

Although formal conflict resolution procedures are rarely documented, communities have developed informal ways to mediate disputes and reach consensus. I5 described this process: “When there are a lot of people, some may disagree. If something doesn't quite make sense, we talk it through, meet, and discuss it. That's how we make decisions that benefit the network.” In some networks, coordinators or designated “godparents” act as mediators.

To exemplify this, the case of Poo'se Ajponũcarõ is useful. A major infrastructure issue—trees and topography preventing a direct connection between the two Indigenous reserves—was resolved by separating the internet providers so both areas could still be served. Interestingly, one of the reserves later decided to stop the network and returned their equipment to Colnodo. Then, the other reserve took the equipment to expand its coverage using 100% of the hardware. The decision was not made by Colnodo, but the communities.

Community networks generally exercise rule-making autonomy, tailoring their regulations to fit local realities and practices. When deciding where to install a router or access point, many factors influence the outcome, including the views of the *grupo gestor*, geographic constraints, financial capacity, and the social profile of the person requesting service (e.g., teacher, student, elder). These decisions rarely follow formal written rules; instead, they emerge from collective discussion and social dynamics. Ostrom (1990) emphasised that in the cases of CPRs that have survived for many years, their rules have been mutating. Those changes over time may be linked to the context of the communities and trial-and-error exercises.

As Stern (2011) mentioned, commons rely on empirical experience and they learn from trial and error. In CNs, governance mechanisms emerge through those practical approaches. For example, La Cachuda lost 20 SIM cards last year, prompting a new rule: appropriators must now pay an inscription fee in addition to their subscription. In cases of equipment failure due to lack of maintenance, each case is assessed individually. As briefly mentioned before, some CNs also regulate usage to avoid network saturation, including PIN-based limits and restrictions on the

number of devices per house. These measures came about after noticing that unregulated access reduced connection speeds.

D4 states, for example, that members are required to inspect physical infrastructure such as antennas, cables, poles, every two weeks. These practices highlight a strong sense of community commitment and collective responsibility for maintaining the network. But, that would be the only active participation of the users.

This reflects other principles identified by Ostrom: monitoring and graduated sanctions mechanisms. In some cases studied, small sanctions are applied when rules are not followed. D2 states that members who miss three meetings or fail to carry out assigned tasks without justification lose their *grupo gestor* status, along with voting rights, and must contribute as general community members. Misuse of services, such as unauthorized PIN sales or sharing, typically leads to monetary penalties and suspension of service. Another example is that those who do not pay on time are subject to reconnection fees, although, as mentioned forehead, flexibility is commonly granted.

Aligned with the principles of the commons, CPR initiatives should have the right to self-organize and be formally recognized by relevant authorities. The CNs studied demonstrate varying degrees of recognition by local and national actors. Participants said that during launch events, representatives from local governments were sometimes present, indicating a symbolic level of acknowledgment. However, this recognition often lacked depth or sustained engagement beyond ceremonial occasions.

At the national level, the current administration under President Gustavo Petro, along with the MinTIC, has taken some concrete steps. In 2023, the government issued the decree 1079 / 2023 that formally regulates and recognizes fixed community internet services. The decree establishes the framework under which community-based connectivity organizations can provide local fixed internet services.

The decree acknowledges the urgent need to expand internet access to underserved and rural areas, particularly among vulnerable and low-income populations. It includes key provisions such as the prohibition of profit for individual

members, a limit of 3,000 service points, and a five-year exemption from the periodic contribution to the Single Fund for Information and Communication Technologies (FUNTIC). However, this regulation applies specifically to fixed internet services, leaving wireless community networks outside of its regulatory framework.

I9 emphasized that recognition must go beyond formal acknowledgment. According to her, authorities should actively support the development of CNs by offering financial resources, such as dedicated funding lines or tailored grant programs. While FUNTIC currently offers a general fund that organizations may apply for, there is still no dedicated program specifically designed to support CNs. She also stressed that support should not be limited to financial aid, it should also include capacity-building and seed funding to equip communities with the technical skills and knowledge necessary to design, implement, and sustain their own networks.

In sum, the governance mechanisms observed in Colombian community networks reflect an adaptive, and context-shaped approach to the management of shared digital infrastructure. Following some of the principles of the commons, these mechanisms emphasize participatory decision-making, community accountability, and flexibility. While these networks vary in their degree of institutionalization and alignment with Ostrom's principles, they share a commitment to participatory decision-making, collective accountability, and the pursuit of community benefit over individual gain.

In addition, it is relevant to acknowledge that the decline in participation in decision-making processes can potentially undermine the democratic principles that community networks aim to uphold. When only a small group of users remains actively engaged, governance challenges may arise, including reduced transparency, accountability, and inclusivity. Such situations can also raise concerns about emerging power imbalances. However, in the cases where CNs remain active, the inclusion of new members into management groups presents a valuable opportunity to revitalize participatory decision-making and more evenly distribute responsibilities. This ongoing renewal helps sustain collective ownership and reinforces the networks' values of collaboration and community autonomy.

Chapter 5: Sovereignty, autonomy and self-determination of Colombian CNs

This chapter explores the complex relationships between community networks, technological sovereignty, and self-determination in the Colombian context. While the global conversation around internet access often emphasizes infrastructure and service provision, community-led initiatives shift the focus toward local control and relevance, and collective agency.

Drawing on theoretical frameworks from scholars such as Couture and Toupin (2019), Pohle & Thiel (2020) and Belli (2017), alongside empirical insights from interviews and fieldwork, this chapter examines how Colombian CNs are designed not merely as tools for connectivity, but as expressions of political autonomy, cultural identity, and social cohesion.

It also critically examines the barriers these networks face, including technical, regulatory, and political challenges, and reflects on the conditions under which CNs can thrive as expressions of autonomy and empowerment. In doing so, it responds to the research question: What challenges do CNs face in sustaining collective action and infrastructure?

5.1 Sovereignty and self-determination

When talking about self-determination and self-sovereignty through the lens of social movements, concepts such as autonomy naturally arise. As seen in the theoretical part, technological sovereignty is employed to “affirm the autonomy of social movements through collective (and sometimes individual) control of technologies and digital infrastructures, and especially their power to develop and use tools which have been designed by them and/or for them,” (Couture & Toupin, 2019, p. 2315).

5.1.1. Autonomy, appropriation and cultural identity

I6 said that the processes of design and build CNs are fundamentally about seeking and strengthening the autonomies of peoples, “We do not want to focus

attention solely on the technology; rather, we want to focus on our processes as a community, as organizations, working together with others.” He emphasized that technologies should be means for achieving greater self-determination, enhanced political influence, and an increased capacity to manage their own education, healthcare and more.

Building on this premise, the organizations leading these processes typically develop methodologies that place the community at the center. These methodologies enable the community to create and design their own rules and infrastructure, and even to articulate their collective dreams and values. For instance, Colnodo employs a methodology that includes a step called “disoñar,” a portmanteau blending the Spanish words for design (*diseñar*) and dream (*soñar*). Of course, questions about the influence or power of the organizations over the communities emerge here. In the case of Colnodo, they bring the methodology but it is the community who walks the path. The decisions about where to install the nodes or how to understand the territory, for example, are based on cartographies made by the community.

Moreover, Couture & Toupin (2019) pointed that communities are mobilized by the desire to satisfy their own needs. To do so and to achieve autonomy and self-determination, communities require active appropriation of technology. This goes beyond simply providing access to computers or the internet. In the cases analyzed, the design and deployment of community networks engage the community in processes of appropriation that encompass not only the technological infrastructure but also the social and cultural fabric. I6 referred to this broader engagement as “meaningful connectivity.”

The concept of Universal and Meaningful Connectivity (UMC) refers to “the possibility for everyone to join a safe, satisfying, enriching, productive and affordable online experience” (ITU, n.d.). Here the focus is not solely on access itself, but on how individuals access and use the internet. According to the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and the United Nations, six dimensions are essential to achieving UMC: connection quality, availability, affordability, appropriation of devices, skills, and security.

Community networks can be seen as advancing toward UMC by providing fast and reliable internet connections, continuous availability, affordable services, and

context-shaped systems. Furthermore, their design and implementation processes prioritize capacity building, secure and meaningful internet use, and the collective appropriation of technology.

I2, for example, explained that people from the communities feel the network was theirs because they build it, literally, with their hands and customized for their needs. And appropriation does not come solely by building the network, other factors can influence those processes, for example the inclusion of original content in the intranet or the reflections about notions of identity. In the cases studied, this is often expressed symbolically, reflecting cultural identity through elements such as the network's name, the names of connection points, and the logos created by the communities.

An example of this is the community network in La Argentina was initially named "Red Nasa Piçkwe Ikh," literally referencing the Indigenous reserve that manages it. However, after some time, the community chose to rename it "Red A' Çxab Wejxa," which means town of communication stars or connection in their language, Nasa Yuwe. Their logo incorporates key symbols from their territory, such as the sun, lagoon, and mountains, while also representing their identity as Nasa people through the inclusion of a ceremonial stick (Colnodo, n.d.-f).

Another example comes from the Poo'se Ajponũcarõ network, where the names of the connection points reflect some of the ethnic groups present in the *resguardos*:

“**Tukano**: installed at the home of Mrs. Arlety Quiroz, located in the upper part of the *resguardo*. **Yuruti**: installed at the home of Mrs. Virginia Suarez, located in the central part of the *resguardo*. **Siriano**: installed at the home of Mrs. I3 Braga, located in the lower part of the *resguardo*. **Piratapuyo**:

installed at the home of Mrs. Yirley Vasca, located in the central part of the *resguardo*,” D4.

5.1.2. Adaptation to community needs

Another important factor to consider is contextual adaptation. As Belli (2017) has argued, self-determination in connectivity implies that communities possess both the right and the capacity to design, develop, organize, and maintain shared network infrastructure. They do so according to their own rules and agreements. As discussed in the previous chapter, Colombian CNs have developed and adapted their governance structures based on core values such as trust, community cohesion, and a focus on youth and education.

The infrastructure itself is built purposely to meet the specific needs of each community. For example, in the case of BolivarWireless, the network initially included a range of offline resources tailored to local priorities, such as chat tools, encyclopedias, educational materials, and more. Yet, in other contexts, the advantages of wireless internet over fixed local connections are especially relevant. Community members often work in agriculture, move frequently across the territory, or guide tours in rural areas, meaning that internet access must be available outside the house.

This need for mobility reflects a broader principle of contextual adaptation, which also extends to the physical design of the infrastructure. In BolivarWireless, for instance, metal cans were repurposed to improve signal direction. “Yes, we used, for example, milk cans or especially the metal cans that wine bottles came in. And that was it. We would point those toward the node, and they would connect to the internet through that,” I8 explained.

5.1.3. Contested control and dependency

Following what Couture and Toupin (2019) mentioned, the control of the technology is made collectively. In the cases studied and as said before, the participation of the community can vary depending on the rules and the context. Control is held by the same community, but other actors also exert it. From the state and the regulations to private actors like local IPS or multinational corporations like Starlink.

The pursuit of autonomy may be undermined by dependence on third parties, particularly private corporations. Representatives from all the organizations interviewed expressed concerns about this reliance, especially when it involves large, powerful companies. For instance, questions arise such as: What if Starlink suddenly raises its prices beyond affordability? (the increase in prices has already been observed) or what if it decides to discontinue service altogether?

These concerns extend beyond practical or technical issues; they also touch on broader debates about independence in internet governance and sovereignty. The influence of major corporations in decision-making processes and service provision represents a critical challenge to the autonomy that CNs strive to uphold.

On this issue, I6 emphasized that there is no reason to demonize the use of private companies for backhaul services, particularly in countries where reliable public local infrastructure is lacking. However, he also stressed that communities should avoid becoming entirely dependent on these providers. I11 echoed this sentiment, noting that such solutions should be viewed as temporary measures rather than definitive answers to connectivity challenges. “It’s important for a country to have its own infrastructure. We see Starlink [or other satellite options] as a short-term solution, something that can be used for now. But when the government eventually arrives with fiber or other solutions, the community can choose between different alternatives”.

This discussion also raises broader questions about state sovereignty over infrastructure. One potential solution lies in government-led initiatives to expand optical fiber networks in rural areas. However, this approach may introduce new concerns, such as political influence over infrastructure projects, or the risk of discontinuity due to changes in government or shifting political priorities.

Nevertheless, reliance on private companies or state initiatives for other elements of the infrastructure appears to be significantly lower. In most of the cases analyzed, communities make use of free and open-source software and hardware as integral components of their networks. For instance, equipment such as routers is sourced from the LibreRouter initiative, and the methodologies employed are often the result of collective, community-driven processes. In the case of Bogota-Mesh, for example, I7, who comes from the Free Software community, sought to replicate not

only the governance dynamics but also the technological practices rooted in openness and collaboration.

5.1.4. Collectiveness

Appropriation stems from both the community's knowledge and their active involvement in the design and construction of the network, as well as from the trust they place in one another. As I15 explained: "I feel that access is easier for us, or that there's more trust among us, as members of the community, and that we ourselves are the ones managing the network. So people feel that sense of trust and security when accessing this network."

In this context, the fact that the community is responsible for managing and maintaining the network frequently emerged in participants' responses when describing the difference between state- or commercially-led initiatives and community networks. This is closely tied to a strong collective identity, which plays a fundamental role in Colombian CNs. I13 introduced a key concept from Black and Afro-Colombian communities: *uramba*. "We are seeking *uramba*, as we say here, which means unity, coming together. Through the Colnodo project and this community network initiative, we have seen that *uramba* in action. We've seen that people are more united, that they participate."

This sense of collectivity has been further strengthened by complementary initiatives developed alongside the CNs. In the case of Almagrande, the entire process has been interwoven with the production of audiovisual content, including a film that won an award at the Montes de María Audiovisual Festival (FAMMA). The film, *Nuestra vida campesina* (Our Peasant Life), portrayed the daily lives of farmers in the *corregimiento* and celebrated the shared experiences and common values that unite the community.

Taken together, self-determination and autonomy manifest in Colombian CNs in varied and context-specific ways. The processes of technological appropriation go hand in hand with the strengthening of the social fabric and the cultivation of a collective sense of community. Throughout the interviews, the notion of social and civic empowerment emerged, often not merely as an outcome of the CNs, but as a driving force behind their creation. The unique characteristics of each territory and

its people play a critical role in shaping the level of autonomy achieved. In line with Ostrom's (1990) observations, communities that share and manage CPRs that are located far from centralized governance structures tend to enjoy greater autonomy.

Moreover, by reclaiming infrastructure and asserting control over their networks, CNs actively practice self-sovereignty according to their own rules and priorities. Their design and governance structures reflect the specific social agreements, technical capacities, and local conditions of each community. In these contexts, technology is not seen as a savior or a universal solution to community problems, but rather as a tool to meet locally defined needs. As I explained:

“Even if technology arrives and they connect to the world, the *campesino* essence must not be lost. There's a territorial identity, traditions, and ancestral paths. Communication should serve that purpose, to tell stories, preserve memory, and improve life. Otherwise, as María Hichaga said of museology: ‘if it doesn't serve life, it serves nothing. We say the same: if the internet doesn't serve life, it serves nothing.’”

To sum, these networks challenge dominant models of top-down infrastructure deployment by centering local knowledge, participatory governance, and cultural values. Autonomy, in this sense, is not a static condition but an ongoing process, shaped by territorial realities, collective decision-making, and strategic negotiation with state and private actors.

While reliance on corporate providers presents risks, the emphasis on open-source technologies, community ownership, and contextual adaptation might mitigate these dependencies. As illustrated by concepts like *uramba* and the integration of audiovisual storytelling, CNs assert that connectivity must serve life, culture, and collective empowerment, not the other way around.

5.2 Challenges

With all of the mentioned above, community networks still present some challenges in terms of governance and sustainability. One of the primary obstacles lies in ensuring economic viability over time. CNs require an initial investment to purchase equipment, followed by ongoing funding for maintenance, technical

support, electricity, and service provision. According to the theory, CNs receive funds from two sources: direct users paying fees or subscriptions and organisations or public funds (Schuler, 1996 as cited in Fuchs, 2017).

In contrast to what the theory said, in the two Bogotá cases, there were no economic models in place. The equipment and other fees were mainly on the hands of the developers and their volunteer work. The students used their money to pay for the modems and antennas. This reflects what Fuchs (2017) mentioned as one big challenge for non-commercial community networks in the goal of offering free or cheap internet access. Especially to be able to survive when there is competition with commercial providers that can offer more stable service.

However, as discussed earlier, in the cases of CNs promoted by Colnodo, they use both forms of funding, an initial seed offered by organizations, and then sustainability fees charged to the users. The support of the former usually covers initial capital investment, especially for infrastructure, such as antennas, modems, electrical equipment and simcards. While this grassroots support has been essential, it is insufficient for long-term and for expansion.

To continue building CNs across the country and reaching more remote or underserved territories, public support from the state will be essential. As Birkinbine (2018) pointed out, communities need political projects to actively incorporate resources from the state into commons infrastructure. As I11 noted, civil society and nonprofit organizations cannot, and should not, be solely responsible for expanding community connectivity. This model is not sustainable in the long run. He argued that the state must take a more active role, particularly by leveraging existing resources: “Countries do have universal service funds. So, allowing community networks to access these funds would be a very good way to start diversifying a country’s network and also to enable interconnections between CNs.”

Following the initial investment, participants in community networks must also dedicate time and effort to learning and practicing technical skills related to internet connectivity. Building and strengthening local capacities is not only central to the deployment process but also essential to the long-term sustainability of CNs. In the majority of interviews conducted for this research, this theme emerged

repeatedly, highlighting the importance of equipping local people with the knowledge required to build and maintain the network infrastructure.

In the projects supported by Colnodo, the technical team uses specific methodologies and trial-and-error learning to transfer knowledge about how the network operates. However, for practical reasons, these trainings are sometimes limited to a small group of individuals, which may lead to knowledge concentration, where only a few people possess the necessary expertise. As I1 explained, in her community, only she and one other person understand how the system works; if they were to leave, the network's autonomy would be affected. That could mean fewer grades of independence.

I9 highlighted that, although some processes took place several years ago, the organization continues to offer technical assistance to the communities that request it. Despite the availability of manuals and initial training, diverse and unexpected technical failures can occur. For this reason, knowledge transfer and skill-building must be continuous, ensuring that communities can adapt and resolve issues independently over time.

This need for continuous training is also relevant to the expansion and replication of community networks. I7, for example, emphasized: "It was about understanding how technology works. So, whenever we did an installation, we would explain what a router was, how it worked, how we configured it, what the function of the antenna was, and what an electromagnetic wave is."

However, participating in training sessions requires available time, which can be challenging, particularly when attendees already hold leadership roles or other responsibilities within the community and their families. This brings up another issue: the need for active and engaged communities. While some literature suggests that CNs promote civic empowerment, the empirical data from this study indicate that civic engagement and community cohesion are often preconditions for the creation and sustainability of a CN, not just outcomes. A strong sense of community, shared values, and social organization are fundamental to every stage of the process.

In addition to the internal challenges faced by community networks, significant obstacles persist at the state and governmental levels. These include the

lack of formal recognition, insufficient financial support, and the absence of a legal and regulatory framework that adequately enables their existence and operation.

On one hand, some local governments and politicians have launched projects aimed at expanding internet access in underserved communities. However, these initiatives often prove unsustainable. When projects fail or political administrations change, the infrastructure is frequently abandoned, leaving behind what several interviewees described as a “cemetery of antennas”—referring to the numerous Wi-Fi, satellite, and network antennas installed by such programs that are now defunct.

On the other hand, as I6 emphasized in the need of recognition by the state: “by recognizing them, also provides access to spectrum, access to infrastructure, financial support, and assistance so that communities can create their own content.” One of the most pressing concerns is the regulation of radio spectrum. As previously discussed, Colombia allocates spectrum primarily through auction-based mechanisms—an approach that overlooks the unique nature of community networks, which differ fundamentally from commercial ISPs in both purpose and capacity. Unlike traditional providers, CNs do not operate under profit-driven models and lack the financial resources to compete in these auctions. Although there are rare cases, such as RedINC, where CNs have successfully obtained spectrum licenses, these remain exceptions rather than the norm.

Civil society organizations have consistently called for regulatory reforms that acknowledge the social function of CNs. These demands include dedicated spectrum allocations, fee exemptions, and policy instruments that ensure equitable access to communication infrastructure. As Ramírez García & Blanco Romero (2021) highlight, such measures are essential to prevent digital exclusion and support the democratization of connectivity.

In Colombia, civil society continues to advocate for the reservation of specific frequency bands for community-driven initiatives, urging the state to formally acknowledge and protect the role of CNs in addressing the digital divide. However, as I9 pointed out, these measures are adapted to the contexts and the communities, for example making the application forms easier to fill out and making the requirements a reflection of what is actually happening in the territory. “When talking about

obligations or compensations, they often refer only to economic ones. But social contributions are being overlooked, which community networks are already making, for example in schools and health centers. So it is about adapting those regulatory conditions accordingly,” she mentioned.

As seen, in Colombian community networks sovereignty is not a static achievement but a dynamic process, negotiated through shared infrastructure, distributed knowledge, and community-driven governance. However, sustaining their autonomy requires ongoing efforts: from maintaining technical skills and resisting dependency on private providers, to navigating complex regulatory environments and ensuring broader state recognition.

The cases discussed show that CNs flourish in contexts where civic engagement and social trust are already strong, and where the network is embedded in broader community efforts. Yet, challenges remain: technical knowledge is often concentrated in a few hands, public policy still marginalizes CNs in spectrum allocation and licences assignation, and financial sustainability remains vulnerable.

Conclusion

By applying Ostrom's design principles alongside theories of internet sovereignty and self-determination, this thesis has provided a framework for analyzing the governance, sustainability, and broader social implications of Colombian community networks. The aim was to foster dialogue between theory and practice, recognizing that local realities in the Global South often challenge, nuance, or extend existing conceptual models. The findings demonstrate how these initiatives function as collectively governed infrastructures that provide alternatives to traditional, corporate-dominated models of connectivity.

Colombian CNs can be understood as infrastructural commons: networks built, owned, and managed by communities that prioritize collective benefit over profit. Beyond providing internet access, these networks foster autonomy, strengthen cultural identity, and act as instruments for exercising digital sovereignty. From a governance perspective, they align strongly with several of Ostrom's principles, including clearly defined boundaries, collective-choice arrangements, and multi-level participation in decision-making and sustainability tasks. However, participation often declines over time, concentrating decision-making power in smaller groups and creating risks for transparency, accountability, and inclusivity. Strengthening participatory mechanisms and expanding technical training could mitigate these challenges.

Community networks are about social cohesion. They need and strengthen the social fabric, enhance trust, and enable collective projects that extend beyond digital access, such as education, cultural initiatives, and community organizing. These networks find a good soil to grow in communities with strong pre-existing organizational structures and robust social capital. As Ostrom notes, communities succeed in commons management when their members "have shared a past and expect to share a future," (1990, p. 88). The cases analyzed reflect this: members share a common context, history, and set of values, motivating them to collaborate in building, maintaining, and sustaining these networks for present and future generations.

Yet, while Ostrom's eight design principles provide a strong foundation for understanding CN governance, they are insufficient to fully capture the complexities of modern internet infrastructure. The interaction between CNs and private actors such as Starlink introduces new dynamics of autonomy and dependency. In these cases, autonomy does not necessarily mean independence from large corporations but rather the ability to exercise sovereignty over decisions about where and how connectivity is provided. This tension reveals one of the most pressing challenges for Colombian CNs: balancing their autonomy with reliance on corporate-controlled infrastructure.

This dependence reflects broader structural inequalities in global telecommunications. As Fuchs (2017) notes, major corporations dominate the internet backbone and face little pressure to negotiate equitable access agreements, leaving CNs dependent on for-profit actors for basic operations. While these networks succeed in expanding connectivity to underserved populations, their emancipatory potential remains constrained by these dependencies.

Despite their linked with social fabric, Colombian CNs do not primarily view themselves as competitors or challengers of private internet providers but as citizen-driven infrastructures that reclaim a degree of control over connectivity (De Filippi & Tréguer, 2015). While only a few members currently hold advanced technical knowledge, knowledge transfer and skill-building are key priorities for strengthening autonomy. In practice, in the cases studied, combating corporate dominance is often less a direct motivation than an indirect outcome of these efforts.

As I12 explained, "the effort [of building and maintaining CNs] is immense, so only those communities with a very strong incentive take it on, either because they are extremely neglected, have significant support, or because they have a deep desire to achieve that autonomy." Understanding CNs thus requires analyzing their human, technical, economic, social, and governance dimensions in an integrated manner.

For CNs to achieve long-term sustainability and fully realize their transformative potential, greater state involvement is crucial. This includes dedicated funding mechanisms, regulatory frameworks tailored to community initiatives, and programs for capacity-building. However, such support must avoid paternalism and instead empower communities.

In sum, Colombian community networks exemplify how commons-based approaches to connectivity can promote inclusion, autonomy, and social transformation. They challenge both state- and corporate-led centralization by building participatory, trust-based infrastructures rooted in community needs. Yet, their survival and growth depend on carefully balancing grassroots innovation with institutional support, proper legal frameworks, and investment in capacity-building.

Finally, CNs are laboratories for collective governance and innovative ways of conceiving and building the internet. As connectivity expands through public, private, and community-driven efforts, those communities still excluded from the digital sphere are among the hardest to reach. Community networks represent a plural, participatory, and sovereign alternative to bridge these gaps and contribute to a more diverse and inclusive digital future.

Limitations and future research

This thesis presents several limitations that should be acknowledged. It relied on a case study approach involving seven Colombian CNs, selected based on accessibility and willingness to participate, which limits the generalizability of findings. In addition, data collection often depended on single representatives per network, leading to partial perspectives and underrepresentation of less active members. Adding to that, the researcher's positionality as an external actor introduced potential confirmation bias. While steps such as transparency in interactions, triangulation of interviews with governance documents, and critical self-reflection were implemented to mitigate this risk, it is acknowledged that the framing of questions and analysis could still have influenced the findings.

Lastly, while Ostrom's design principles offered a robust analytical framework, commons framework itself has limitations in fully capturing the complexities of modern digital infrastructures and the entanglement of community networks with state and corporate actors. These conceptual boundaries highlight the need for theoretical refinements that move beyond rigidly categorizing commons governance through a fixed set of principles. Commons are inherently flexible and adaptive, and treating Ostrom's eight principles as a checklist risks undermining the qualities that sustain them. This research incorporated perspectives from sovereignty

and self-determination theories to enrich the discussion, adding nuance and broadening the analytical lens.

Future research should deepen the analysis of CNs' interactions with corporate and state actors, particularly regarding spectrum allocation, backbone dependency, and regulatory integration. Also, deeper discussions about power imbalances and comparative studies across different regions in the Global South could illuminate how diverse political, economic, and cultural contexts shape CN governance. Additionally, further investigation into participatory strategies for expanding technical knowledge within communities could support their long-term resilience.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Interview protocols

Interview protocol for participants of CNs

Part i. Context and motivations

1. What is the context in which this network is being developed?
2. What were the motivations behind building a CN?
3. What kind of participants are involved in the process of construction, implementation and management of the CN?
4. Which obstacles did/does the network face?
5. Why are you using this CN? Instead of other providers
6. What is your role in the network and for how long have you been involved?
7. What are the main priorities the builders of this network have?
8. Which stakeholders are involved in these processes and how?

Part ii. Questions about governance

9. Are there social norms or rules that must be followed and respected to join the network?
10. Are they written somewhere?
11. How can members of the community participate in the decision-making processes?
12. If there are conflicts, how can they be solved? Are there sanctions involved? Give examples if known.
13. Who is monitoring the network and the compliance with the norms?
14. Is there anyone being excluded from the decision-making process or the governance mechanisms?
15. Is there any kind of exchange of knowledge with other CNs?
 - If yes, how did it happen and how is it useful if so?

Part iii. Questions about sovereignty.

16. Is this CN recognized by external authorities?
17. Is there any difference between CNs and commercial providers in terms of access and use?
18. What are the tangible effects of building and using your own network?

Interview protocol for organizations boosting and promoting CNs

Part i. Context and motivations

1. What is the context in which community networks are being developed?
2. Why promote CNs?
3. Is there any value in building CNs?
4. What is the contribution of CNs in terms of Internet governance?
5. How is self-sovereignty seen in CNs?
6. Are CNs sustainable in the long term?
7. What are the tangible effects of building and using your own network?
8. To build their networks, communities are using providers that are commercial, giant, and private, such as Starlink or Azteca Comunicaciones. Is there any risk to their autonomy or governance in using those networks?

Questions to ask to the documents

1. Who can join the network?
2. What governance mechanisms does this community use?
3. Which actors are involved in the process?
4. What are the tools used to communicate with the other participants of the network?
5. Check 8 design principles

Appendix 2: Thematic Codebook

Following the categories (Parent Node), codes (Child Node), a short definition of the codes.

1. Governance methods

Code	Definition	Use When...
Governance structures	References on how the governance mechanisms are made. Are they different levels in the governance structures?	They mention management groups, management structures and nested groups or thematic divisions.

Meetings & Communication	References to formal or informal gatherings for decision-making. Include channels of communication and notifications.	Mention of assemblies, councils, or casual planning meetings. Someone talks about coordination or communication related to the network.
Decision-making	Descriptions of how decisions are made within the CN.	There is mention of consensus, voting, leadership authority, or conflict.
Rule-making autonomy	The ability of the community to set its own rules and norms.	References to policies or norms created by the community.
Monitoring & sanctions	Descriptions of oversight, compliance, or enforcement mechanisms.	Mentions of who ensures rules are followed or penalizes rule-breaking.
Conflict resolution	How disputes are resolved in the community or about the network.	Discussions of conflict management methods or examples.
Shared resources/ responsibilities	Mention to tasks, commitments on the use and maintenance of the network. Network treated as a collectively managed asset.	Commitments on who is allowed to use the network, who contributes, collective responsibilities and ownership.

2. Participants

Code	Definition	Use When...
Role in the community	Describes a person's place in the social or cultural structure.	The interviewee talks about being a teacher, leader, parent, etc.
Role in the CNS	Specific technical, leadership, or support roles in the community network.	They mention managing the router, organizing meetings, etc.

Inclusion/ exclusion	References to who participates or is left out of decisions or access.	Mentions of gender, age, power, or social hierarchies.
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3. Motivations

Code	Definition	Use When...
Economic reasons	CN helps with saving money, income, or avoiding telecom costs.	Mention of affordability, economic benefit.
Social reasons	Motivation to improve social ties, communication, or community strength.	Talks about unity, connection, mutual help.
Educational reasons	Need for education access, school support, and knowledge.	Mentions of students, teachers, educational goals.
Connectivity reasons	Lack of connection to the internet, bridging access to internet and technology inequality.	References to lack of service, absence of providers, marginalization.
Personal growth	Using the CN to improve persona performance, preserve identity	Talks about life projects, personal improvement.
Political resistance	The CN as a form of opposition to the state or market.	References to activism, resistance, distrust in institutions.

4. Sustainability

Code	Definition	Use When...

Economic models	How the CN is financed or generates money.	Talks about contributions, payments.
Infrastructure maintenance	Keeping the hardware and physical network running.	Mentions of repairs, upgrades, or hardware challenges.
Transfer of knowledge/Building skills	Efforts to train people in managing the CN. Mentions of engineers, NGOs, or other supporters.	Workshops, tech leaders, or skill-building.
Social cohesion	References to social fabric and collectiveness.	Talks about collectiveness to maintain the CN.
External support	Reliance on or resistance to external NGOs or funders.	Mentions of partnerships, funding, or NGO roles.

5. Sovereignty

Code	Definition	Use When...
Appropriation	Community feels that the CN is “theirs.”	Talks about pride, responsibility, protection.
Contextual adaptation	CN practices adapted to local context (terrain, culture).	Local solutions to problems and adaptation to their singularity
Independence from market	Deliberate distance from corporate actors.	Talks about differences between commercial providers.
Recognition before authorities	CN receives attention or validation from outside actors.	Talks about visits, academic interest and legal recognition.